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Paper 1

**THE INFLUENCE OF AMERICAN STOCK MARKET OVER THE
CRYPTOCURRENCY MARKET-A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF S&P 500 And
BITCOIN**

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ABSTRACT

S&P 500 is very likely to have an influence on the cryptocurrency market which is represented by the bitcoin. This study is an effort to analyze how the S&P500 Index of the US dictates the market prices of Bitcoin over a specified period of time. Secondary data has been used, tabulated, and analysed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS where in standard deviations and correlations were calculated and regression analysis was carried out for the Index values. From the study, it became quite evident that the S&P500 Index indeed has a thrilling influence on the market price of Bitcoins.

Key Words: S&P 500, Bitcoin, Risk, Return, Index Values.

Introduction:

The Standard and Poor's 500, sometimes known as the S&P 500, is an index used to measure the performance of 500 of the biggest firms listed on American stock markets. It is one of the equity indices that is most often followed. According to polls, more than \$7.1 trillion was invested in assets linked to the performance of the index as of December 31, 2021. The S&P 500 index is a capitalization- and free-float-weighted index. The Conference Board Leading Economic Index, which is intended to forecast the direction of the economy, includes the index as one of its determining variables. Depending on the market or website, the index has a number of ticker symbols linked with it, including \$SPX and GSPC.INX. S&P Dow Jones Indices, a joint venture owned mostly by S&P Global, maintains the S&P 500, and a committee selects each of its constituents.

Any type of money that exists digitally or virtually and uses cryptography to secure transactions is referred to as a cryptocurrency, also known as a crypto. Cryptocurrencies use a decentralized system to track transactions and create new units instead of a central authority to issue new currency or regulate them. In January 2009, the mysterious and pseudonymous Satoshi Nakamoto introduced Bitcoin, a decentralized digital money that is based on his white paper's principles. The price movement of Bitcoin, the most well-known cryptocurrency, has a significant effect on the rest of the market for cryptocurrencies. When compared to the total market capitalization of the entire crypto market, the market capitalization of Bitcoin

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stands at 52.72%, indicating that it is the world's largest cryptocurrency and controls the entire crypto industry.

Objective of the Study:

- This study is mainly undertaken to understand the risk and return of S&P 500 and Bitcoin.
- The study aims to analyze the relationship between S&P 500 and the Bitcoin.

Literature Review:

Bitcoin's emergence as the first fully decentralized digital payment system in the world is a revolutionary development for the financial markets. This essay focuses on the price swings of bitcoin and examines if investing in digital currencies like bitcoin is a viable option. The relationship between the price of bitcoin and a few different variables, such as the stock price index, oil price, and the daily volume of bitcoin trading, has been demonstrated using cointegration analysis and the VEC (Vector Error Correction) Model. According to empirical study, there is an equilibrium over the long run as well as a dynamic interaction over the short term among the four components. According to the short-term analysis, the impact of stock price index is significantly greater than that of oil price and bitcoin trading volume (J. Wang et al., 2016).

For the financial markets, Bitcoin's emergence as the first completely decentralized digital payment system in the world is a revolutionary development. This essay focuses on the fluctuations in the price of bitcoin and considers whether it is wise to invest in such virtual money. Cointegration analysis and the VEC (Vector Error Correction) Model have been used to show the relationship between the price of bitcoin and a few different variables, including the stock price index, oil price, and the daily volume of bitcoin trading. Empirical research indicates that there is both a long-term equilibrium and a dynamic interplay between the four components in the short term. The influence of the stock price index is substantially bigger than that, according the short-term research (Lahiani et al., 2020).

Using a vector autoregressive model, this article examines the connection between Bitcoin and the stock market. Utilizing the Sliding Window approach, the impulse response signal is enhanced. The findings of the study demonstrate the connection between Bitcoin and the stock market. First, while the S&P 500 has a weak impact on Bitcoin, the S&P 500 has a rather substantial impact on it. The mean of the Dow Jones and the standard deviation of the S&P 500 both have remarkably strong effects on the mean of Bitcoin after the Sliding Window technique is used, and the standard deviation of the S&P 500 also has a relatively significant impact on the standard deviation of Bitcoin (X. Wang et al., 2020).

We examine the development of informational efficiency in 16 international stock markets and 45 cryptocurrency exchanges prior to and during the COVID-19 pandemic. To determine the degrees of stability and irregularity in cryptocurrencies and global stock markets, the largest Lyapunov exponent

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(LLE) based on Rosenstein's approach and approximate entropy (ApEn), which are resilient to small samples, are applied to price time series. The degree of regularity suggests that fluctuations are unpredictable. On the estimated LLE and ApEn, the t-test and F-test are run. To examine for variations across time periods (pre- vs during COVID-19 pandemic samples), as well as to check for discrepancies between markets (cryptocurrencies versus equities), a total of 36 statistical tests are run. It was discovered that during the COVID-19 pandemic period, (a) the level of stability in cryptocurrency markets significantly decreased while the level of irregularity significantly augmented, (b) the level of stability in international equity markets remained constant but increased irregularity, (c) cryptocurrencies became more volatile, (d) the variability in stability and irregularity in equities was unaffected, and (e) cryptocurrency and stock markets exhibit a similar pattern (Lahmiri & Bekiros, 2020).

Through the use of the wavelet coherence technique and the Markov switching autoregressive model, this study investigates the behaviour of the stock markets and cryptocurrency marketplaces during the COVID-19 pandemic. Our findings point to a financial contagion in March as both stock prices and cryptocurrency experienced significant declines. Cryptocurrencies quickly recovered despite this decline, but stock markets are still stuck in the bear market. In other words, we see that the type of market affects the price dynamics during the pandemic. Since some hedging characteristics can be discovered in the cryptocurrency response to such a severe occurrence, these findings are important for investors (Mohd Thas Thaker & Ah Mand, 2021).

The study carried out a thorough assessment of the relationship between cryptocurrencies and the stock market. This study examined 151 publications from November 2021 to November 2008 using bibliometric and content analysis. We investigated the influential elements of the literature, including the well-known organizations, authors, nations, and journals, using VOS viewer software. To further our understanding of the network, we also conducted co-authorship, bibliographic coupling, and keyword co-occurrence analyses. In addition, we covered the important conclusions of the four main study streams in the content analysis. Finally, we provide seven potential research questions for consideration. The findings have a variety of consequences for the literature on cryptocurrencies and the stock market as it stands right now, including study gaps and potential future research endeavors (Jeris et al., 2022).

Due to its close reliance on economic fundamentals, financial speculation, and fragile emotions in large numbers of traders, the stock market is extremely dangerous for investors. The purpose of this study is to determine whether widely accepted safe-haven assets, such as bitcoin, gold, and commodities, may offer investors useful hedging utility in global stock markets, particularly during times of intense market instability. First, we discover that commodities like gold, bitcoin, and commodities can only have mediocre hedging impacts on stock markets when employing the spillover index method based on the TVP-VAR

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model. Commodities, gold, and bitcoin are listed in order of strength as safe havens. Second, we have noticed that these safe-haven investments generally have a greater potential to hedge against market volatility. Strangely, the world stock market and established stock markets operate as the net spillover transmitters, while bitcoin, gold, and commodities act as the net recipients, in the safe-haven asset market. Last but not least, the overall spillover effects change over time and become much more pronounced following the occurrence of exceptional occurrences (Q. Wang et al., 2022).

Since the start of active Bitcoin trading, the Covid-19 bear market offers the first significant market losses. This market correction offers an opportune opportunity to test the much discussed safe haven qualities of Bitcoin. In this study, we demonstrate that, rather than serving as a safe haven, the price of Bitcoin declines in lockstep with the S&P 500 as the crisis worsens. Even a tiny investment to Bitcoin significantly raises portfolio downside risk when held alongside the S&P 500. Our empirical results raise questions about Bitcoin's capacity to shield established markets from volatility (Thomas Conlon*, 2020).

In order to determine the market phase, we apply hidden Markov models (HMMs) and hidden semi-Markov models (HSMMs) on Bitcoin/US dollar (BTC/USD). We draw comparable conclusions to Standard and Poor's 500 (S and P 500), a standard stock index that serves as a benchmark and is the subject of several financial studies. Market phases are commonly referred to as "bull," "bear," "correction," and "rally." To make sure that states are appropriately classified in terms of market phase labels, we fit HMMs and HSMMs and examine the evolution of hidden state parameters and state persistence parameters over time in the first section. We conclude that four-state HSMMs provide the best modeling results for both the S&P 500 and BTC/USD. Our modeling methodologies also offer favorable outcomes for both markets (Suda & Spiteri, 2019).

The definition of comparative analysis and how it differs from analysis in general are covered in the first section of the article. Then, based on (a) whether they seek to explain differences or similarities and (b) the assumptions they make for the underlying causal patterns that are evident, it distinguishes four types of comparative analysis. Although the former contrast is well recognized, it is contended that the later contrast is essential and provides access to numerous pathways of comparative study that would not otherwise be available. The argument is universal even though the examples are taken from the field of housing and urban studies. The definition of comparative analysis, its primary forms, the research designs required to do it, and some of the issues that come up are all covered in turn in this article (Pickvance, 2001).

According to the empirical findings, the SV-t model is better suited to account for outliers and can, to some extent, characterize extreme values. First, the ARSV-t model yields a more accurate fit than the

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MFSV model; second, the effects of positive and negative shocks on volatility are not equal. Asai Manabu (2008). Our findings demonstrate the Markov Chain's effectiveness for our sample as well as its convergence and stability for all parameters up to a predetermined threshold. Our findings support Dyhrberg's (2016) research and refute Baur et al.'s (2018a, b) assertion that bitcoin has distinct risk-return characteristics and a different volatility mechanism than other assets (Hachicha & Hachicha, 2021).

Previous research on the relationship and cause between the S&P 500 and Bitcoin, as well as their functions during recessions, served as the foundation for this study. Using data from reliable sources and statistical software analysis, this study uses quantitative research methodologies to investigate how the connection and causality between the two assets changed during the epidemic. The Granger causality test and the Pearson correlation coefficient are tools used to assess the relationship between the S&P 500 and Bitcoin across the given periods of time (Andersson & Fankl, n.d.).

Research Methodology:

This study is mainly undertaken to understand influence of S&P500 on Bitcoin. We have considered daily closing values of S&P500 as well as Bitcoin for 16 years starting from 2006 to 2022. The expected return has been calculated by simply taking average of index value for the said period. Yearly returns for both S&P500 and Bitcoin was calculated in the following manner:

- Yearly returns of S&P500 (1)

$$YR = \text{Current year return} - \text{Previous year return}$$

- Percentage returns had been calculated on the yearly return of S&P500 (2)

- Yearly return of Bitcoin (3)

$$YR = \text{Current year returns} - \text{Previous year returns}$$

- Percentage return has been calculated on the daily return of Bitcoin (4)

- Standard Deviation has been determined for both S&P500 and Bitcoin in order to measure the risk of each of the index. The standard deviation is measured to understand how far the deviations of each index from the average, of which the higher reading indicative of higher risk involved in each index and Vice versa. Here the formula to measure Standard deviation $\{\sigma\}$:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{s=1}^n (r_s - \bar{r})^2}$$

Where: σ = Standard deviation of Index.

n = No. of observation.

$r[s]$ = return of index.

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- Regression analysis has been done to know the extend of relationship between S&P500 and Bitcoin.
- Percentage returns are plotted on the scattered diagram for the analysis.

Hypothesis:

H₀: There is no significant corelation between the index values of S&P500 and the Bitcoin.

H₁: There is significant correlation between the index values of S&P500 and Bitcoin.

Data Analysis & Interpretation:

Table1 indicates the average annual returns and the percentage annual returns of both S&P500 Index and that of the Bitcoin and the overall standard deviation of both.

Table 1: Average Annual Returns And Percentage Annual Returns of S&P500 And Bitcoin.

	S&P500		Bitcoin	
	Annual Return (1)	% Return (2)	Annual Return (3)	% Return (4)
03/31/11	1325.83			
03/30/12	82.64	6.233077	4	400
03/28/13	160.72	11.41096	88	1760
03/31/14	303.15	19.31888	365	392.4731
03/31/15	195.55	10.44415	-212	-46.2882
03/31/16	-8.15	-0.39412	167	67.88618
03/31/17	302.98	14.70962	655	158.5956
03/29/18	278.15	11.77245	5858	548.5019
03/29/19	193.53	7.328267	-2807	-40.5284
03/31/20	-249.81	-8.81351	2363	57.36829
03/31/21	1388.3	53.71452	52450	809.1638
03/31/22	557.52	14.03311	-13172	-22.3512
03/31/23	-421.1	-9.29496	-17368	-37.9545
		SD		SD
		28.03957		487.7898

Source: As computed by the Authors

Observation:

- In 2020 we can observe the ill effect of the Covid-19 Pandemic on the US stock market which was not felt in the cryptocurrency market for the same period.
- It has been observed in 2022 that, The Bitcoin has generated negative returns due to the bad effect of Russia Ukraine war and it was not felt by the American Stock market in the same period.

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- In the year 2023, both the American stock market and Crypto market generated negative returns due to the fears of interest rate hike by the US Fed to tame the hiking inflation in the US economy.

Table 2 shows the Correlation of the S&P500 Index and the Bitcoin. The Karl Pearson’s Correlation has been used to understand the relationship between the S&P 500 and the Bitcoin.

Table1: Independent-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
S&P50 & Bitcoin	12	337.2389	525.81126	151.78864

Table 2: Independent--Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
S&P50 & Bitcoin	2.222	11	.048	337.23888	3.1543	671.3234

Source: As computed by the Authors

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The P value obtained is 0.048 as a result of which the null Hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance implying that there is significant correlation between the Index value of S&P500 And Bitcoin.

Chart 1: The chart shows Historical % Returns by comparing percentage yearly returns of both S&P 500 and Bitcoin

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Chart 2: The table shows the regression between S&P500 and the Bitcoin where S&P500 is the independent variable and the Bitcoin is the dependent variable.

After the regression analysis, the equation obtained is $y = -60.695x + 792.45$ $R^2 = 0.1732$ where Y stands for S&P500 index value and X for Bitcoin value and 1% increase or decrease in the value of S&P500 causes -60.695 corresponding increase or decrease in the Bitcoin value

Findings:

From the above analysis, we have found that:

- There is a significant correlation between the Index values of the S&P500 and the Bitcoin and therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected as per the paired samples test (Table 2).
- The movements in both the indices are not correlated and in most of the cases S&P500 has not dictated the movement of Bitcoin (Table 1).
- The regression equation shows that 1% increase or decrease in the value of S&P500 cause -60.695 corresponding increase or decrease in the value of Bitcoin.

Conclusion:

Being the economic indicator of the biggest economy in the world the S&P500 is very likely to have an obvious influence on the Cryptocurrency market which is represented by the Bitcoin. This study has analysed how S&P500 dictates the prices of Bitcoin over a specified period of time. The study has found that S&P500 index has telling influence on Bitcoin. In addition to that it has been observed that there is a significant correlation between S&P500 and the Bitcoin.

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Paper 2

POLICY ISSUES IN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Government policy in education is a multifaceted area that shape the structure, content, and accessibility of learning. It encompasses decisions on funding, curriculum development, teacher training, assess to education, and more. These policies influence the quality of education, student outcomes, and societal progress. Understanding and evaluating these policies is crucial to fostering an inclusive, effective, and equitable educational system. Government policies on education vary significantly from country to country and often undergo changes overtime. India’s education policy as recently undergone a significant transformation with the introduction of National Education Policy (NEP) in 2020. This policy emphasizes several key aspects, including a shift towards a more holistic and flexible approach to learning, the integration of technology, promotion of multilingualism, and an emphasis on skill development and vocational training. It also aims to restructure the curriculum to focus on conceptual understanding and critical thinking rather than rote memorization. The NEP also advocates for greater autonomy and flexibility in higher education, encouraging multidisciplinary studies and research. However, effective implementation of these policies at all levels remains a challenge and subject of ongoing discussion and evaluation.

Objectives: The main purpose of this paper is to review the government policy on education and to assess the implementation hurdles of NEP. The specific objectives are;

1. To review and to discuss on New Education policy.
2. To understand the policy implementation problems in India.

Method: Paper is descriptive reviewing the policy documents and the existing literature on education policy.

Discussions: Discussions on education policy will focus on mainly changes in the policy from the earlier existed education system and benefits to the students like entry-exist, employability, industry educations links etc.

Key words: Government policy, New Education Policy, Implementation hurdles.

Government policies in education cover a wide range of topics, from curriculum standards and funding allocation to teacher training and assessments. Some critical issues include access to quality education for all, addressing disparities among different socio-economic groups, integrating technology effectively, fostering inclusive learning environments, ensuring teacher quality and support, and adapting education to meet the demands of a rapidly changing job market. These policies play a crucial role in shaping the future of education and the opportunities available to learners.

Government policies on education vary widely across different countries and regions. They often aim to address various challenges and meet specific objectives within the education system. The effectiveness

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of these policies depends on their implementation, funding and adaptability to changing societal needs.

Some common areas covered by education policies include:

1. **Access and Equity:** Policies often focus on ensuring that education is accessible to all, regardless of socio-economic background, ethnicity, or location.
2. **Curriculum and Standards:** Governments set educational standards, curricula, and learning outcomes to ensure quality education and standardized learning experiences across the country.
3. **Teacher Training and Support:** Policies may prioritize continuous professional development for teachers, offering training programs and support to improve teaching quality.
4. **Technology Integration:** Recognizing the importance of technology in education, policies may aim to integrate it effectively into classrooms to enhance learning experiences.
5. **Inclusive education:** There might be policies aimed at creating inclusive environments for students with disabilities or special needs, ensuring they receive adequate support and opportunities for education.
6. **Assessment and Accountability:** Governments often implement assessment systems to measure student performance, teacher effectiveness, and overall school accountability.
7. **Higher Education Policies:** This includes funding strategies, student loan programs, and initiatives to promote access to higher education.

The success and impact of these policies can vary based on the political climate, available resources, stakeholder collaboration, and the degree of public involvement. Some policies might face challenges in implementation due to budget constraints, bureaucratic hurdles, or resistance from various stakeholders. Regular evaluations and updates to policies are essential to adapt to evolving educational needs and societal changes.

II. Literature Review

‘PARADIGM SHIFT IN HIGHER EDUCATION PROPOSED BY NEP 2020: A HUMANISTIC APPROACH Sourav Bandopadhyaya, Nandini Rooj & Dr. Arnab Kumar Dutt in their article tried to review the proposals of NEP 2020 and its implementation in higher education system followed by a humanistic approach. The relationship between humanistic approach and learning was studied, the relationship between heutagogy and learning are examined, the purpose of implementing heutagogy in higher education system is explored, and tried to find out how NEP 2020 incorporate heutagogical approach.

Fostering Environmental Literacy through the Curriculum at School Level: NEP 2020's Approach and its Implications, Anshul Saluja while studying Fostering Environmental Literacy through the curriculum

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at school level emphasis on Environmental literacy which is essential for individuals to comprehend, appreciate, and appropriately solve the urgent environmental issues affecting our globe. This article explains how NEP 2020 anticipates the inclusion of environmental literacy in the overall school curriculum and considers any potential effects on students, teachers, and the community at large.

In his paper NEP 2020: Implementation challenges DR. BINNYBEN MEHTA explains National Education Policy (NEP). Along with the benefits of NEP he explains the challenges in the implementation of NEP in schools and Higher Education. The author concludes that the implementation of NEP is no easy task. This requires a cultural shift in the entire higher education ecosystem, over the next 15-20 years. According to the author to realize the dreams it contains, we must overcome substantial execution challenges in a sustained manner for years and decades to come.

NEP 2020's "Light but Tight" Approach to Address the Key Challenges of Education in India-Dr. Mohammad Amin Dar. Dr. Mohammad Amin Dar focuses mostly on how the adoption of NEP 2020's can bring about radical changes in teacher education in India. It discusses how well teacher education programmes in India will accomplish their goals, paying particular attention to ongoing professional growth, cutting-edge teaching techniques, and multimodal teacher training. Another question the author tries to answer is, what is the "Light but Tight approach" from NEP 2020, and how can its adoption in teacher education be successful? Finally, the author discusses how NEP 2020's proposals may be put into practice and how the goals it established could be met within the time frame specified.

Problems, Obstacles, and Suggestions for Improving the Quality of Higher Education Institutions in NEP, Dr. V. Vijaya Lakshmi. Dr. T. Ugandhar explains the benefits of NEP and also tries to explain the hurdles in the implementation of the NEP 2020. They say that the policy has an impressive view, but the real difficulty is in actually putting it into practice. They hold the opinion that several states will object. According to them NEP's most difficult challenge is simultaneously fixing several flaws in the educational system. The above said article sums up saying cooperative federalism and state ownership of the reforms are crucial for the NEP's success.

III. Hurdles in the implementation of new education policy

The implementation of a new education policy often faces several hurdles that can hinder its successful execution. The New Education Policy (NEP) in any country is no exception. Some common challenges include:

1. Resource allocation: Implementing new policies often requires significant financial resources. Adequate funding must be allocated to training teachers, updating infrastructure, developing new curriculum materials, and providing necessary technology.
2. Resistance to Change: There might be resistance from various stakeholders, including teachers,

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administrators, and parents, who may be accustomed to existing systems or have concerns about the existing system.

3. Capacity building: Training and retraining teachers and educational staff to align with the new policy objectives can be time-consuming and resource-intensive.

4. Infrastructure and Access: Ensuring that all regions, particularly rural areas, have access to the necessary infrastructure, technology, and resources can be a challenge.

5. Policy Coordination: Sometimes, different levels of government or departments within the education sector might not coordinate effectively, leading to discrepancies in implementation strategies.

6. Evaluation and Monitoring: Establishing robust mechanisms for monitoring progress, evaluating outcomes, and making necessary adjustments is crucial but can be complex to institute.

7. Long-term Commitment: Education policy implementation requires long-term commitment and continuity, which can be challenging in political climates where priorities might shift with changes in leadership.

Overcoming these hurdles often requires a multi-faceted approach, including clear communication about the benefits of the new policy, engagement with stakeholders for their buy-in, phased implementation strategies, capacity building, and continuous monitoring and evaluation to make necessary adjustments.

IV. Review on New Education Policy

The New Education Policy (NEP) introduced in various countries aims to revamp and modernize the education system, addressing emerging challenges and adapting to the needs of a rapidly changing world. The NEP typically includes a comprehensive framework that encompasses various aspects of education. Some key points often highlighted in the NEP include:

1. Holistic Approach: Emphasizes a holistic and multidisciplinary approach to learning, integrating various subjects and skills rather than compartmentalizing education.
2. Flexibility and Choice: Provides flexibility in choosing subjects and streams, allowing students to follow their interests and talents, promoting a more personalized learning.
3. Early Childhood Education: Focuses on early childhood care and education, recognizing the critical importance of foundational learning in the early years.
4. Skill Development: Emphasizes skill development, vocational training, and practical learning opportunities to prepare students for the workforce and entrepreneurship.
5. Technology Integration: Acknowledges the role of technology in education and aims to integrate it effectively into teaching and learning processes.
6. Assessment Reforms: Encourages a shift from rote memorization to competency-based assessment, focusing on evaluating a student's overall development and skills.

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7. **Teacher Training and Professional Development:** Prioritizes continuous professional development for teachers, ensuring they are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to implement the new pedagogical approaches.

The success of the NEP depends on effective implementation strategies, adequate resource allocation, stakeholder engagement, and regular evaluation and adjustments based on feedback and evolving needs. While it often presents a promising vision for education, its impact ultimately relies on the commitment and collaboration of all involved parties, including policymakers, educators, parents and students.

The New Education Policy (NEP) documents in various countries, including India, generally encompass comprehensive frameworks outlining the vision, objectives, strategies, and guidelines for transforming the education sector. These documents are typically extensive and cover a wide range of aspects related to education reform.

Here's descriptive review of typical NEP documents:

1. **Vision and Objectives:** NEP documents start with a clear articulation of the vision for the future of education, highlighting key objectives such as holistic learning, skill development, inclusive education, and leveraging technology for enhanced learning experiences.
2. **Educational Structure:** They often discuss proposed changes in the educational structure, including the restructuring of school stages, curriculum framework, and the integration of vocational and higher education.
3. **Curriculum and Pedagogy:** Detailed sections outline proposed changes in curriculum design, emphasizing flexibility, multidisciplinary learning, and experiential learning approaches. They may suggest new methodologies to encourage critical thinking and problem-solving skills.
4. **Assessment and Evaluation:** Discussions on assessment reforms form a significant part, advocating for shifts from rote memorization based assessments to competency-based evaluations and formative assessments.
5. **Technology Integration:** Given the role of technology in modern education, NEP documents often highlight plans for integrating technology effectively into the learning process, promoting digital literacy, and ensuring access to digital resources.
6. **Implementation Strategies:** They outline proposed timelines, phases of implementation, suggested policies for funding allocation, stakeholder engagement, and monitoring mechanisms to ensure successful execution.

These documents are comprehensive roadmaps that outline the aspirations, goals, and strategies for transforming the education landscape. They serve as guiding documents for policy makers, educators, and stakeholders to align their efforts towards achieving the outlined objectives within the education sector.

V. Conclusion

In conclusion, navigating government policy issues and overcoming hurdles in implementation remains a persistent challenge. Specifically, the National Education Policy (NEP) encounters obstacle due to

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varying regional needs, resource allocation, and resistance to change within existing educational frameworks. To address these challenges effectively, collaboration between stakeholders, sustained public engagement, adaptive strategies, and a commitment to flexibility will be vital. By prioritizing inclusivity, innovation and continuous evaluation, the path toward successful policy implementation, particularly in the realm of education reform, can be paved for the benefit of society as a whole.

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Paper 3

**DISTANCE EDUCATION:
A NEW PERSPECTIVE FOR SELF PACED LEARNING**

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ABSTRACT

Distance education have become one powerful medium of obtaining degrees for large number of students who are staying in far off and remote areas and for whom accessing universities on a regular basis is still a dream. Distance learning is a form of learning in which students and teachers are not present in the same place or time but use different means of communication to facilitate the teaching –learning process. The present research article focuses on distance education a new prospector for self paced learning. The present paper is a thematic paper. In the conclusion the investigator opines that distance education provides flexibility affordability and high quality education accessible from anywhere.

Students’ curiosity to learn new things is triggered by self-paced learning. They nurture a willingness to try things out, view and handle problems from different perspectives, and long for change, while they take pleasure in learning

Keywords: Distance learning, self paced learning

Distance education

Distance education also known as distance learning is the education of students who may not always be physically present at school or where the learner and the teacher are separated in both time and distance.

Self paced learning

Distance education allows students to progress through the course work at their own pace. This flexibility is particularly beneficial for self motivated learners who prefer to take more time on challenging topics or accelerate through material they are familiar with.

INTRODUCTION

Distance education began through the use of postcards by Issacc Pitman in 1840. Sir Issac Pitman used to send postcards to students. He taught a system of stenography by mailing steno graphically translated texts and postcards and receiving transcripts from students for proof reading. The University of London was the first to launch a distance learning course in the 1858. This is said to be the formal initiation of distance learning. Wolsey Hall, Oxford is the first distance learning college in the UK which was founded in 1894.

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Wolsey Hall, Oxford is the largest home schooling college in the world which offers various courses in primary, secondary, IGCSE and many other A- level subjects. It offers distance education to more than 120 different countries.

Distance learning is a relatively new concept in India. It only dates back to the early 1960s In the year 1961, in India the Central Adversary Board for Education established a committee chaired by Dr.D.S.Kethari to make important suggestions regarding the nature, scope and structure of distance learning course.

In India the first distance education center was established in 1962 by the University of Delhi. It was later renamed as the school of correspondence course and continuing education.

Distance enrolment constitutes 11% of the total enrolment in higher education as per AISHE Repeat: 2017-18

Student enrolment in universities under distance mode (As per UGC Annual report 2017-18)

Year	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18
No. of students enrolled in Distance Education	38,11,723	38,24,901	40,89,781	40,31,594

Year	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19
No of Universities/Institutions recognized to offer programmers through distance mode	157	130	114	118	104

Concept of self learning

In self-learning, also called self-directed learning, the emphasis is laid on the learner capability to learn according to his/her needs, interest, ability and pace. According to Knowles(1975,p.18), ‘self-directed learning’ is a progress by which individuals take the initiative, with or without the assistance of others, in diagnosing their learning needs, formulating learning goals, identifying human and material resources for learning, choosing and implementing appropriate learning strategies, and evaluating outcomes, Knowles(1975 and 1984) differentiated adult learning (andragogy) from child learning(pedagogy). His thinking s based on the premise that in the case of adult learners there is a steady increase in their need and capacity to:

- be self-directing in their study;
- make use of their life experience in learning;
- identify their own readiness to learn; an
- Organize their own learning around real experiences.

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Advantages of distance learning for students and parents

Today’s colleges have better methods of teaching their students, thanks to the rise of technology. Traditionally, Computer laboratories were available in the majority of classrooms, enabling students to gain required digital literacy skills in preparation for further education and their future employment.

- One advantage of technology that the young generation today has is the option of distance learning. The idea has no doubt brought fresh ways with which technology can be utilized for teaching the students and the concept has been successful so far, no matter for what level or grades it is used.
- Popular and known educational Institutes like NMIMS were already providing distance courses for years and the arrival of the pandemic added fuel to the concept as students got highly comfortable and familiar with the process of taking from home. Now, more and more education seekers are choosing the option of studying from the comfort of their homes and are happily accepting distance learning courses.

The first and foremost advantages of distance learning is

1. Time saving
2. Flexible schedules–
3. Unmatchable accessibility–
4. Reduces travelling pressure–
5. Reduces expense–

One of the reasons why e-learning programs are cost-effective is that they require less time for training (in terms of travel, study materials, trainers, and accommodations).

6. Responsibilities and self-discipline-

Online programs require youngsters to be self-starters despite being convenient. There are deadlines to meet even though you study at your own speed and time.

7. Parents get to know about their children’s circle–

It is possible that you haven’t yet met everyone in your child’s large circle of friends. However, you’ll be more aware of what’s going on in your child’s social life if you get to casually observe a digital study session.

8. Increases the Involvement of Parents-

Since students complete their online courses from the comfort of their homes, parents get the opportunity to be directly involved in the studies of their children.

Advantages of self paced learning

- The benefits of self-paced learning can be different in terms of the types of learner it develops. However in common, here are some of the importance and benefits of self-paced learning.
 1. Learning at their own pace

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- During self-study, students learn at their own pace, focusing more on areas that interest them the most or that which they understand better.
- 2. Develops ownership of learning
- This act of children taking up complete ownership of their learning can result in a sweep of knowledge for themselves.
- They become their own masters. By self-learning, students build an immense sense of self-confidence that helps them deal with all possibilities of their life.

3. Better insights into learning

Students have a variety of learning modes to choose from. It could be from YouTube tutorials, books, podcasts, webinars, discussions, polls, or activity walls, as they wish. Online learning software has most of these including self-learning through quizzes, PDFs, assignments, etc. All that the students need to do is to choose the one that suits them the most that they find the most engaging and move on.

Mobile tools as learning aids have become a part of higher institutions now.

- Learners demonstrate greater awareness
- Self-directed learners demonstrate greater awareness while dealing with commitments.
- Willingness to try out new things and learn new skills

4. . Students become an expert

Students develop a sense of accountability to comply with rules and become efficient and in genuine.

5. Prompts more effective learning in students

Self-learners experience effective learning as they actively engage with whatever they learn.

6. Boosts self-esteem and self-reflection of students

By self-learning students become more confident learners

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the level of distance learning
- To compare the distance learning as a self paced learning
- To find out the effect of demographic variables such as gender and type of family for distance learning

Hypothesis of the study

- The impact of distance learning on improving self paced learning skills of pupils of Kasaragod district.
- There will be no significant difference between distance learning as a self paced learning of pupils of Kasaragod district with regard to type of family

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- There will be no significant gender difference in distance as a self paced learning among the pupils of Kasaragod district

RESEARCH DESIGN, TOOLS

The design of the study is correlation in nature, so a correlation research design was used in the present study.

TOOLS

Questionnaire

SAMPLE

The investigator has taken 200 students from Kasaragod district who are undergoing distance education from different Universities like IGNOU, Annamalai, Kannur.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The statistical techniques used for the present study are descriptive and inferential statistics Descriptive statistics like mean, median, mode.

Standard deviation Skewness, Kurtosis are used to understand the present status of the distribution of variable on this sample.

Correlation and regression: Correlation and Regression are the two multivariate distribution based analysis. A multivariate distribution is called multiple variables distribution.

Correlation described as the analysis that allows us to know the relationship between two variables ‘x’ and ‘y’ or the absence.

RESULTS

	Distance Learning
Mean	33.90
Median	35.00
Mode	43
Std. Deviation	8.171
Skewness	-.511

	Self Paced Learning
Mean	19.76
Median	21.00
Mode	23
Std. Deviation	11.190
Skewness	.265

	TYPE OF FAMILY	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	P value
DISTANCE LEARNING	Nuclear	88	34.64	8.280	1.13	.260
	Extended	112	33.32	8.074		
SELF PACED LEARNING	Nuclear	88	23.36	11.165	4.20	.000
	Extended	112	16.93	10.411		

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		DISTANCE LEARNING	SELF PACED LEARNING
DISTANCE LEARNING	Pearson Correlation	1	-.170*
	Sig.(2-tailed)		.016
	N	200	200
SELF PACED LEARNING	Pearson Correlation	-.170*	1
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.016	
	N	200	200
• Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)			

DISCUSSIONS

Result of this research study are as follows

1. The measures of central tendency and variation like mean, median, mode, standard deviations and Skewness of distance learning students shows that the distributions are positively more scores are lying on the right side of the distribution for distance learning and self paced learning..
2. The result indicates that majority of the students have average level of distance learning and high level of self paced learning
3. There is no significant difference in distance learning and self paced learning .
4. There is no significant relationship between distance learning and self paced learning.
5. There is no significant gender difference in distance learning and self paced learning.
6. Female students have high self paced learning.

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. The study was undertaken to know how far the distance learning and self paced learning are interrelated.
2. The findings of the study may add to existing knowledge in this area and will be beneficial to understand his complicated variables.
3. Result of the study will help to plan strategies and create awareness about the different perspectives of education
4. The study may be conducted on different age groups and sex with different demographical backgrounds.
5. Further study may be conducted by using different designs other than those employed in this study.
6. The researcher has great hopes and faith that the research with the help of many children who are undergoing the distance education will be of great help in their future career.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

1. The present study has particularly added an under respected population in the distance education and self learning. However while interpreting the result of the study careful consideration must be taken while generalizing the result to other age group.
2. Since the study conducted on adolescent sample belonging from rural area, the same cannot be generalized for urban population.

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3. Further the sample size of the study is 200 of Kasaragod District, Kerala State, which represents typical Indian culture. India being multi-cultural country considerations should be taken while generalizing the results to the whole of the country.
4. Furthermore, the measures used in the study were all self-report, which brings in the tendency of possible bias. There are changes of some variations plus chances contribute to the current literature.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Further research could focus on extending the study to large geographical area since it provides more information on the differences in these variables.

- In future, more detailed research can be undertaken with respect to other independent variables like age sex, culture, religion, physical health etc.
- The result only considered 200 samples which is not too large. So conducting research using a large sample will produce more generalisable result.
- Current research considered two variables distance learning and self learning Therefore adding more variables like psychological and subjective well being will make research more advanced.
- The present study investigated research on a limited number of adults only.

Therefore a large number of people, especially those of different age groups are included in future studies.

Conclusion

Distance education's potential advantage involves increased educational access. It produces a high quality learning opportunity, improves student outcomes and skills and expands educational choice options. Therefore location, time and quality are no longer considered factors in scaling degree courses or higher education because of distance learning. Distance learning provides a bright future to one education with its positive probability. The concept of self-paced learning or self-directed learning, particularly in distance education system, is essentially characterized by:

- A learner-centered approach to teaching and learning;
- Learner's responsibility for his/her own learning;
- Flexible provision of education to meet individual needs, interests and requirements;

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Paper 4

“ENHANCING LEARNING THROUGH COLLABORATIVE VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENTS: A COMPREHENSIVE EXPLORATION AND ANALYSIS”

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This paper aims to investigate the impact of collaborative virtual environments on learning outcomes, examining the effectiveness of such platforms in fostering engagement, knowledge retention, and collaborative learning experiences. Additionally, the paper seeks to identify key design principles and best practices for the successful integration of collaborative virtual environments into educational settings, providing insights for educators, instructional designers, and policymakers to optimize the use of these innovative tools in the learning process.

Methodology / Design / Approaches: It is an exploratory study with the help of secondary data where the researchers have conducted a content analysis of various magazines, articles, Google Scholar, data-based and related websites.

Findings and results: The findings provide valuable information for teachers trying to optimize their Digital Learning Environments, as the integration of shared virtual environments is strongly enhancing student engagement, boosting knowledge retention and promoting interaction with students.

Originality/value: It is a comprehensive exploration and analysis, which synthesizes empirical research to reveal subtle insights into the transformative potential of collective virtual environments to contribute value to developing innovative and efficient learning methods.

Type of Paper: Descriptive research with exploratory research design.

Keywords: Collaborative, Innovation, Education, Policymakers, Knowledge, Learning, Best Practice.

I. INTRODUCTION

Collaborative virtual environment refers to spaces in which users from different parts of the world can work together, communicate and cooperate on a real time basis. In order to simulate the experience of Immersive and Interactivity, these environments often use technologies like VR, AR or Mixed Reality. Collaborative virtual environments seek to replicate the spontaneity and interactivity of face to face collaboration in a virtual world, unlike traditional eLearning platforms. Collaborative virtual environments offer a number of advantages Firstly, they create an immersive learning environment which encourages active participation [1]. In order to improve their understanding and retention of knowledge, learners may use simulations, virtual field trips or interactive scenarios in order to study the complexities of concepts. In addition, Collaborative virtual environments promote collaboration and teamwork which allows users to cooperate on projects, solving problems in a collective way or exchanging ideas without geographic

obstacles. There are also a number of challenges posed by Collaborative virtual environments [2]. A widespread adoption may be impeded by technological limitations, e.g. hardware requirements, network connectivity and compatibility with software. In addition, in order to ensure that all learners can benefit from these environments, the design of effective Collaborative virtual environments requires careful consideration of their usability, accessibility and inclusion. In addition, the protection of user data and promotion of responsible online behavior need to be addressed in relation to privacy, security as well as digital citizenship [3]. A profound change in the education system. It's going to get even more sophisticated, Immersive and Ubiquitous as technology keeps evolving [4]. The promise of democratizing access to education, geographical and socioeconomic obstacles for learning is contained in this development. In addition, Collaborative virtual environments have the potential to revolutionize professional development, remote collaboration and lifelong learning initiatives that will enable individuals to acquire new skills and knowledge in a variety of fields [5]. In essence, the exploration and analysis of collaborative virtual worlds provides valuable insight into a wide range of educational technology's functions in terms of enriching education experiences, fostering collaboration as well as driving innovation towards knowledge accumulation [6].

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It is an exploratory study with the help of secondary data where the researchers have conducted a content analysis of various magazines, articles, Google scholar, data-based and related websites.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To find out about the current state of collaboration virtual environments.
2. To analyses the educational theory and pedagogical framework that underpins collaborative learning in the virtual environment.
3. To assess the impact of the collaborative virtual environment on students' academic performance and learning outcomes.
4. To examine the outcome of collaboration virtual environments based on SWOC analyses.

III. 1. Current State of Collaborative Virtual Environments

Education and Training Applications In education and training, collaborative virtual environments have gained traction. It provides interactive experiences that allow students to interact with content and each other in a shared virtual environment. Technological Advancements Virtual reality technologies have been instrumental in developing more accurate and effective collaborative artificial environments [7]. Platform Diversity Support for collaborative virtual environments has evolved through a number of platforms and tools. Some focus on specific sectors, while others are broader in scope. Platforms for health training, engineering simulations and digital learning are examples. Social Presence and Interaction this includes the integration of realistic avatars, natural gestures, and spatial audio to create a sense of co-presence among users. Remote collaboration and telepresence. Teamwork and communication across geographic borders can be facilitated by these environments [8].

III. 2. Educational theories and pedagogical frameworks

Constructivism, which demonstrates that learning is built on interaction with the environment. This

means that students are actively interacting with digital content and each other in virtual collaborative settings to develop their understanding. Social Constructivism is the importance of social interactions in learning, suggesting that meaningful learning occurs through collaboration and communication [9]. This theory is compatible with the collaborative nature of virtual environments where students can cooperate, share ideas and build their knowledge on a collective basis [10]. Connectives is a new theory, focusing on the importance of networks and technology in education which stresses the role played by Internet connections and collaborative platforms to shape knowledge. Pedagogical frameworks such as Problem Based Learning and Project Learning are also influential because they promote the development of collaborative solutions to problems in virtual environments.

III. 3. Influence of collaborative virtual environments on students' academic performance and learning outcomes

The Researcher shows the assessment of the influence of collaborative virtual environments on students' academic performance and learning outcomes involves a comprehensive exploration and analysis of various factors. It characterized by interactive and shared digital spaces, offer students a unique platform for collaborative learning, enabling them to engage in joint activities, discussions, and problem-solving exercises [11]. Studies indicate that the integration of collaborative virtual environments in educational settings fosters increased student engagement, active participation, and a sense of shared responsibility, which positively impact academic performance [12]. Researcher observed collaborative virtual environments provides opportunities for experiential learning, allowing students to apply theoretical knowledge in practical scenarios, thus enhancing their understanding and retention [13].

III. 4. SWOC analyses of collaboration virtual environments

A SWOC analysis is a strategic planning tool to assess the strength, weakness, opportunities and challenges of particular situations or initiatives. The analysis helps to understand the factors which may affect their efficiency when it comes to collaboration virtual environments such as online platforms or tools for facilitating teamwork and communication. For collaboration virtual environments, here is how SWOC analysis can be applied:

1. Strengths

Accessibility: Virtual environments enable collaboration regardless of geographical location, allowing team members to work together remotely.

Flexibility: These platforms often offer a variety of communication channels (e.g., chat, video conferencing, file sharing) to accommodate different collaboration needs.

Scalability: Virtual environments can support both small teams and large organizations, adapting to changing requirements.

Integration: Many collaboration tools integrate with other software and services, enhancing productivity and workflow efficiency.

2. Weaknesses

Technical Issues: Virtual environments may suffer from connectivity problems, software glitches, or compatibility issues that disrupt collaboration.

Learning Curve: Users, especially those unfamiliar with technology, may find it challenging to navigate

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and utilize all features effectively.

Security Concerns: Maintaining data privacy and protecting sensitive information can be a concern in virtual environments, especially in industries with strict regulations.

Dependence on Technology: Reliance on virtual environments can pose risks if there are system failures or if users become overly dependent on digital communication at the expense of face-to-face interaction.

3. Opportunities

Global Collaboration: Virtual environments enable collaboration across time zones and borders, opening up opportunities for international partnerships and diverse perspectives.

Innovation: Continuous advancements in technology offer opportunities to enhance collaboration tools with new features, improving efficiency and effectiveness [14].

Remote Work Trends: The increasing acceptance of remote work creates opportunities for virtual collaboration environments to become essential tools for businesses and organizations.

Customization: There's room for innovation in creating tailored virtual environments that cater to specific industries or collaboration needs.

4. Challenges

Cultural Differences: Collaborating virtually may exacerbate cultural misunderstandings or communication barriers, requiring strategies for cultural sensitivity and effective cross-cultural communication.

Team Cohesion: Building and maintaining team cohesion can be challenging in virtual environments, where face-to-face interaction is limited.

Overload: The abundance of communication channels and information in virtual environments can lead to information overload, reducing productivity and increasing stress [15].

Legal and Regulatory Compliance: Ensuring compliance with data protection laws and industry regulations presents challenges, especially in highly regulated sectors like healthcare or finance.

FINDING AND RESULTS

The Researcher found the role of communication and teamwork within collaborative virtual environments, as effective collaboration is linked to improved learning outcomes. Monitoring and feedback mechanisms within these environments contribute to personalized learning experiences, tailoring educational content to individual needs. Overall, assessing collaborative virtual environments impact on academic performance necessitates a nuanced examination of their role in promoting collaborative learning, communication, and personalized educational experiences.

SUGGESTION

Providing clear guidelines for collaboration, facilitating effective communication channels, and incorporating assessment tools within the virtual space can ensure that learning objectives are met. Regular feedback and reflection opportunities can further enhance the learning process in collaborative virtual environments, fostering a sense of community and shared responsibility among learners.

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Paper 5

The Impact of Digital Media on Education Reporting: Navigating Global Challenges and Trends

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This research explores how digital media transforms education reporting globally. In today's journalism landscape, digital platforms play a crucial role, especially in education reporting. The study delves into the impact of digital media on disseminating educational information, analysing challenges, and emerging trends. As traditional news adapts to digital advancements, the research navigates opportunities and obstacles faced by journalists covering education on a global scale. Through a focused analysis, the paper contributes to understanding the evolving dynamics of digital media in education reporting.

Methodology / Design /Approaches: This section outlines the research methodology employed in the study. It discusses data collection methods, including content analysis of education-related news articles, interviews with journalists, and surveys of media consumers. The goal is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the current state of education reporting in the digital media landscape.

Findings and Result: Digital media significantly transforms global education reporting, playing a pivotal role in today's journalism. It shapes the dissemination of educational information, posing challenges, and reflecting emerging trends. As traditional news adapts to digital changes, the study pinpoints opportunities and obstacles faced by global education journalists.

Originality/ Value: Through content analysis, interviews, and surveys, it uncovers challenges and trends, providing valuable insights into the dynamic interplay between digital media and global education narratives.

Type of the paper: Integrated Analysis.

Key word: Journalism, Global Education, Media, Digital Media, Reporting.

1. Introduction

The field of education reporting now sits at the nexus of cutting-edge technical innovations and traditional journalism in the quickly changing digital landscape of today [1]. The global dissemination, consumption, and understanding of educational information have undergone a fundamental transformation due to the growth of digital media channels. With the emergence of social media and data visualisation technologies, educators, journalists, policymakers, and stakeholders are all negotiating a challenging landscape that is being moulded by the proliferation of information sources, shifting audience preferences, and developing reporting techniques [2].

By examining the difficulties and patterns that characterise this ever-changing environment, this study aims to investigate the complex effects of digital media on reporting on education[3].As we investigate this further, it becomes clear that digital media has had a significant impact on the very nature of the narratives themselves as well as on how educational stories are delivered. The traditional boundaries of education

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reporting have broadened, presenting previously unheard-of chances for involvement, analysis, and critique. Examples of these innovations include interactive multimedia pieces and live streaming of classrooms.

Education reporters work in a complicated ecosystem with rapidly evolving social norms and quick technical breakthroughs, all against the backdrop of global difficulties including disinformation, the digital divide, and privacy concerns[4]. This study aims to provide stakeholders with a comprehensive grasp of the benefits and challenges that come with living in the digital era by evaluating the effects of digital media on education reporting. We want to provide educators, journalists, and policymakers the knowledge and skills they need to fully utilise digital media to promote educational discourse and educate the public through an examination of global case studies, best practices, and emerging trends.

2. Digital media

Digital media, as used in education reporting, refers to a broad range of technology tools and platforms that make it easier to create, distribute, and consume educational content. These consist of, but are not restricted to:

2.1 Social Media Platforms: Social media sites like Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Twitter have become effective means of sharing news, insights, and opinions about education [5]. Reporters covering education frequently use these channels to disseminate breaking news, interact with readers, and expand the scope of their reporting. In addition, social media provides a platform for conversation, idea sharing, and collaboration on educational projects among educators, students, policymakers, and experts.

2.2 Online News Portals and Websites: As conventional print media has declined, a lot of reporters covering education have turned their attention to online news portals and websites [6]. Multimedia storytelling, in-depth analysis, and investigative reporting are all made possible by these internet platforms. Moreover, interactive elements like polls, quizzes, and comment sections are frequently available on online news sources, allowing readers to interact more actively and dynamically with instructional content.

2.3 The emergence of educational blogs and vlogs: has brought about a democratic approach to the exchange and distribution of knowledge [7]. Blogger, WordPress, Medium, and other blogging platforms are used by journalists, subject matter experts, and educators to produce articles, guides, and opinion pieces on a variety of educational subjects [8]. Teachers are also using popular video-sharing websites like Vimeo and YouTube to make and distribute documentaries, lectures, and instructional videos.

2.4 Podcasts and Webinars: Educational content may now be delivered in audio and video formats through podcasts and webinars, which have become popular channels. Reporters covering education frequently conduct expert interviews, trend discussions, and debates on divisive topics on podcasts and webinars. These platforms give users an easy-to-use means of staying up to date on the most recent advancements in education and engaging with stimulating information while on the go.

2.5 Tools for Data Visualisation: Infographics, charts, and interactive maps are examples of data visualisation tools that are essential for improving the impact and clarity of reporting in education [9]. By presenting complex data sets in an aesthetically pleasing and simple-to-understand fashion, journalists may help readers quickly pick up on important trends and insights. Additionally, data visualisation makes it easier for reporters to produce stories based on data, revealing inequities, connections, and patterns within the education sector.

2.6 Mobile Applications: The way parents, instructors, and students access educational resources and information has been completely transformed by mobile applications. Numerous features, such as online learning modules, study tools, homework planners, and communication facilities, are available in educational apps. Additionally, news aggregator applications compile instructional content from other sources and offer users customised news feeds based on their choices and areas of interest.

3. Impact of Digital Media on Education Reporting

The creation, distribution, and consumption of educational information are all being altered by the significant and varied effects of digital media on education reporting. There has been a shift away from traditional print media and towards online platforms, such as social networking sites like LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter. These are dynamic venues where education reporters can interact with a

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range of audiences, share research findings, and distribute news. Social media also encourages a lively interchange of ideas and viewpoints by facilitating collaboration and dialogue amongst educators, students, policymakers, and experts.

Education reporters now have more options for in-depth research and multimedia storytelling thanks to the growth of online news portals and websites. Readers can connect more actively with instructional information on these digital platforms by using interactive features like polls, quizzes, and comment areas. Furthermore, educators, journalists, and subject matter experts are now able to write articles, tutorials, and opinion pieces on a variety of themes thanks to the democratisation of information sharing through educational blogs and vlogs. With the help of video-sharing websites like Vimeo and YouTube, educational films, lectures, and documentaries can now be found online, meeting the needs of a diverse range of learners.

A growing number of people are using podcasts and webinars to deliver educational content in audio and video formats. These platforms provide audiences that want to stay up to date on the newest advancements in education with accessibility and ease. By means of conducting interviews, talks, and debates, education reporters employ these platforms to further explore contemporary patterns and controversial topics, so enhancing the quality of educational discourse.

Additionally, by displaying complicated data sets in aesthetically pleasing ways, data visualisation technologies significantly improve the impact and clarity of instructional reporting[10]. Data-driven storytelling can be facilitated and hidden patterns within the education sector can be uncovered by journalists using interactive maps, charts, and infographics to effectively communicate important findings and trends.

With a plethora of features including homework planners, study aides, online learning modules, and communication tools, mobile applications have completely changed how people access educational materials and information. By further selecting instructional information from a variety of sources, news aggregator apps give consumers customised news feeds based on their tastes and areas of interest.

In general, the use of digital media in education reporting has changed conventional methods and created new avenues for participation, analysis, and cooperation. It does, however, also bring with it difficulties including handling information overload, guaranteeing data accuracy, and resolving gaps in digital literacy. It is essential for education reporters to comprehend these dynamics in order to properly traverse the changing landscape and promote educated public discourse on educational issues [11].

4. Research methodology

This research paper employs a secondary data analysis methodology, utilizing existing literature, reports, and scholarly articles to examine the impact of digital media on education reporting globally. Through comprehensive review and synthesis, this study aims to elucidate key trends, challenges, and opportunities within the intersection of digital media and education journalism [12].

5.Objectives of the study

- To examine the influence of digital media on education reporting globally in today’s era.
- To identify challenges faced by education reporters in the digital age
- To explore emerging trends and best practices in digital education reporting through social media.
- Discuss on the citizen journalism in digital education reporting.

5.1 Global Influence of Digital Media on Education Reporting:

The way that educational information is disseminated, accessed, and understood worldwide has changed dramatically as a result of the global impact of digital media on education reporting [13]. Social media

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sites like Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter provide dynamic avenues for education reporters to share breaking news, interact with a variety of audiences, and expand the reach of their reporting in today's connected world. These forums also encourage cooperation and communication between academics, learners, decision-makers, and specialists, influencing the course of conversation in education around the world. The reach and influence of education reporting have also been further enhanced by the growth of online news portals, instructional blogs, podcasts, and webinars, which present chances for in-depth research, multimedia storytelling, and data-driven insights. ‘

Education reporters use technology to improve the calibre, reach, and engagement of their reporting on education around the globe [14]. They accomplish this by integrating digital media tools and platforms into their work.

Furthermore, by displaying complicated information in aesthetically pleasing ways, data visualisation technologies significantly improve the impact and clarity of education reporting [15].

The education sector can benefit from improved understanding and analysis thanks to the effective communication of significant insights and trends by journalists through the use of infographics, charts, and interactive maps. By offering users customisable news aggregator apps, study tools, and online learning modules based on their interests and preferences, mobile applications help democratise access to educational materials even more. Global education discourse in the digital age is being shaped by education reporting's adaptation to new technologies and platforms as digital media continues to develop.

5.2 Challenges in Education Reporting Amidst Digital Advancements

Journalists face a wide range of obstacles while navigating this rapidly changing world as digital innovations continue to transform the field of school reporting [16]. The amount of information that is available through digital media is a major concern. This can cause information overload and make it difficult to identify reliable sources among the deluge of content. Furthermore, social media platforms' quick news distribution can aid in the spread of false information and fake news, which is a serious obstacle for education reporters who work to maintain truth and journalistic integrity.

Moreover, sustaining audience trust and engagement in the digital age is challenging [17]. Education writers must come up with creative ways to draw in and hold the interest of readers despite the cacophony of the digital sphere, given the attention spans of readers getting shorter and the overwhelming number of competing sources fighting for their attention. Education reporters must also navigate a context where authority and competence are frequently questioned, given the democratisation of information creation through blogs, vlogs, and social media platforms, which is further blurring conventional gatekeeping responsibilities.

Furthermore, the emergence of digital innovations has presented education journalists with ethical and privacy challenges, especially when covering delicate subjects like student data privacy or educational disparities. In the digital age, finding a balance between maintaining people's right to privacy and openness is a constant struggle [18]. Ultimately, journalists need to meet these problems head-on as digital technologies continue to transform education reporting. They need to modify their methods to successfully negotiate the intricacies of the digital environment while adhering to the standards of responsible journalism [19].

5.3 Exploring Trends in Digital Education Reporting via Social Media:

The introduction of social media platforms has had a significant impact on the reporting landscape in education [20]. These online platforms are now essential hubs for education journalists to share breaking news, interact with a variety of audiences, and identify new trends in the area. Education reporters have never-before-seen chances to publish multimedia information, expand their reach, and create deep

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conversations amongst experts, students, legislators, and educators on platforms like Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Twitter [21]. Journalists may remain ahead of the curve, find fresh story possibilities, and engage with viewers in real-time by utilising social media analytics and trending topic tracking.

Social media also acts as a spark for innovation in education reporting, helping live reporting, interactive storytelling, and audience involvement programmes to become more widely adopted. Education reporters use social media to tell compelling stories that captivate readers everywhere [22]. They do this by organising Facebook Live events and Twitter discussions, gathering user-generated content, and crowdsourcing story ideas. Education reporters need to stay on the lookout for new trends in social media and adjust their techniques accordingly. By utilising these digital platforms to their fullest, education reporters can use them to influence the direction of reporting on education in the digital era [23].

5.3 Citizen Journalism in Digital Education Reporting: Empowering Voices:

In digital education reporting, citizen journalism has become a potent force that amplifies voices and opinions beyond those of established news channels. Social media and user-generated content platforms have made it possible for people from a variety of backgrounds to report on topics that are important to them and to contribute to the discourse in education. The express personal knowledge, perspectives, and concerns about education, which enhances the narrative and promotes a more inclusive conversation.

Additionally, citizen journalism is essential to reporting on digital education since it helps to unearth stories from the ground up and throw light on regional problems that may go unnoticed by the mainstream media [24]. Citizen journalists offer insightful viewpoints on subjects like educational disparities, creative teaching techniques, and community-led projects via blogs, vlogs, social media posts, and online forums [25]. Citizen journalists help to a more nuanced awareness of the opportunities and challenges within the education sector by elevating their voices and directly interacting with their viewers. This, in turn, leads to good change at the grassroots level.

5.4 SWOC analysis of Impact of Digital Media on Education Reporting:

5.4.1 Strength

- **Broad Reach:** Education reporters can rapidly share material with a worldwide audience by using digital media channels, which eliminates geographical constraints.
- **Multimedia Storytelling:** With the help of digital media, reporters can use a range of forms, including infographics, videos, and interactive information, which improves reader engagement and comprehension of educational topics.
- **Real-time Updates:** Social media platforms give education journalists access to breaking news and events in real-time, facilitating timely and pertinent reporting.

5.4.2 Weakness

- **Information Overload:** Reporters may find it difficult to sort through and validate reliable sources due to the deluge of information that is available on digital media.
- **Misinformation:** The speed at which news is shared on digital platforms can also contribute to the spread of fake news and misinformation, which damages the authority of reporting on education.
- **Digital Divide:** Differences in access to and coverage of information arise from the fact that not everyone has equal access to digital media platforms, especially in underprivileged regions.
- **Short Attention Spans:** In an age of digital distractions, it can be difficult to draw in and hold the interest of readers for educational content, especially in light of the popularity of sensationalist headlines and clickbait.

5.4.3 Opportunities

- **Global Collaboration:** Education reporters may work together with peers, subject matter experts, and readers throughout the globe thanks to digital media, which promotes cross-cultural dialogue and cooperative storytelling.
- **Innovative Storytelling:** Using digital resources, reporters can experiment with new techniques like interactive narratives, augmented reality, and virtual reality to provide audiences a more immersive experience.
- **Audience Segmentation:** With the help of digital media, journalists may customise their reporting to appeal to a range of interests, preferences, and learning styles.
- **Activism and Advocacy:** Digital media gives education reporters a platform to engage in activism and advocacy, enabling them to spread the word about important problems, rally support, and promote social change.
- **Ongoing Education:** Education reporters can stay informed on new developments, industry best practices, and research findings in the field of education thanks to digital media's provision of chances for lifetime learning.

5.4.4 Challenges

- **Data accessibility:** Due to the wide variety of educational environments and the quickly changing nature of digital technology, gathering thorough and trustworthy data on the influence of digital media on education reporting may be difficult.
- **Subjectivity:** Various stakeholders may have various perspectives of the advantages, disadvantages, opportunities, and threats associated with digital media in education reporting, hence evaluating these aspects requires subjective assessment and interpretation.
- **Complexity:** There are many different technical, social, cultural, and economic aspects that play a role in the complex and multidimensional effects of digital media on education reporting. Careful thought and proficiency in media studies and education are necessary for a thorough analysis of these intricacies.
- **Quick Change:** The platforms and technologies used in digital media are always changing, bringing with them new opportunities and difficulties for education reporting. For both scholars and practitioners, it can be difficult to stay on top of these developments and predict future trends.

6. Findings and Suggestions:

By reaching a wider audience and having a greater influence, the emergence of digital media has completely changed the field of education reporting. Reporters are able to instantly distribute information by using social media, online news portals, and educational blogs. This allows for the dismantling of geographical boundaries and the creation of widespread access to educational content. Furthermore, the use of interactive content, infographics, and videos in multimedia storytelling has improved audience engagement and understanding of educational topics. Social media platforms' real-time updates have improved the timeliness and relevancy of education reporting even more by allowing journalists to stay up to current on breaking news and happenings in the field.

Reporters can connect with a variety of stakeholders and get feedback on educational themes by allowing audience contact through comments, shares, and polls, which also promotes a sense of community and engagement. By displaying complicated data in simple-to-understand formats and enabling effective transmission of important insights and trends to audiences worldwide, the use of data visualisation technologies has also significantly improved the impact and clarity of education reporting.

To increase their reach and successfully connect a variety of audiences, education reporters need to keep utilising the possibilities of digital media platforms. To create engaging and educational content that connects with viewers, this means embracing cutting-edge storytelling techniques and experimenting with

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multimedia formats. But journalists still have a responsibility to maintain truth and credibility in the face of the wide range of information that is available on digital platforms. Fact-checking and source verification should always come first, especially when it comes to battling the spread of false information and fake news that are so common in the digital sphere. Establishing collaborations and partnerships with stakeholders from all sectors of the education sector, such as educators, policymakers, and community people, is crucial for enhancing the educational discourse and revealing fresh viewpoints.

It's also critical to stay up to date on new developments and best practices in education reporting and digital media. Journalists can acquire the skills and information needed to successfully traverse the ever-changing world of digital journalism through ongoing professional development and training programmes. And last, in the digital age of education reporting, moral principles like upholding integrity and protecting private rights ought to always come first. Education reporters can guarantee ethical reporting that is meaningful and serves the public interest by upholding ethical standards.

7. Conclusion:

There is no denying the revolutionary impact of digital media on the field of education reporting. A complex interaction of potential and constraints on a global scale has been revealed by the convergence of digital media and education reporting, leading to important discoveries and consequences. Digital media creates opportunities for new forms of information sharing and community involvement, but it also raises concerns about ethical standards, trustworthiness, and responsible technology use, all of which need consideration. Reporters covering education must continue to be dedicated to maintaining the values of truthfulness, responsibility, and integrity as they traverse this ever-changing terrain. Education reporters can maintain their ability to promote educated discourse, effect positive change, and influence the direction of education reporting in the digital era by using digital platforms responsibly and ethically.

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Paper 6

“A STUDY ON STUDENTS’ PERCEPTION ON INTERNSHIP BASED CURRICULUM”

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates how students apply their theoretical knowledge gained in academic settings to real-world problems and situations encountered during active internship placements. The research explores the effectiveness of internships in bridging the gap between theoretical learning and practical application, analysing the challenges and benefits of applying learned concepts in dynamic workplace environments. The study aims to identify students opportunities, challenges and the practical skills they gain during their course of internship. The study was conducted for college students of Mangalore Taluk and the data was collected from 60 respondents by a Google form survey. The study conclude that internship is a viable activity for the learning and growth of students. Practical experience, teamwork, exposure to real world problems were found as a chief outcomes of internship in terms of professional development of students.

Keywords: Internships, theoretical knowledge, Practical skills, Professional development.

INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly evolving workforce, the relevance of traditional education is under increasing scrutiny. The gap between theoretical knowledge gleaned in classrooms and practical skills demanded by real-world workplaces has become a glaring concern. This is where internship-based curriculums emerge as a potent solution, offering a paradigm shift in educational experience. This study delves into the intriguing world of combining formal education with immersive professional exposure. We embark on a journey to explore the theoretical underpinnings, practical implementation models and impactful outcomes of integrating internships into the very fabric of academic programs.

In the dynamic landscape of contemporary education, the emphasis on experiential learning has become more pronounced than ever before. Students are no longer confined to the traditional confines of textbooks and classrooms; rather, there is a growing recognition of the pivotal role internships play in shaping their educational journey. This research embarks on a comprehensive exploration, delving into the intricate layers of students' perceptions regarding an Internship-Based Curriculum.

Traditionally, education has been synonymous with theoretical knowledge disseminated within the four walls of a classroom. However, the evolving demands of the global workforce call for a paradigm shift. The integration of internships into academic curricula has emerged as a strategic response, offering students a bridge between theoretical understanding and real-world application.

While the infusion of internships into curricula is a well-intentioned move, its effectiveness hinges on how students perceive and engage with this shift. Understanding these perceptions is not merely an academic

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exercise; it is a crucial step toward optimizing internship programs to meet the expectations and needs of contemporary learners.

INTERNSHIP

Internship refers to a temporary position or period of work experience offered by organizations to individuals, typically students or recent graduates. During an internship, individuals, known as interns, work within a company or organization for a specific duration, gaining practical, hands-on experience in a particular field or industry. Internships are structured to provide exposure to the professional environment, allowing interns to apply and enhance their academic knowledge in real-world scenarios.

TRADITIONAL METHOD OF TEACHING

The term "theoretical teaching" refers to an instructional approach that primarily focuses on conveying theoretical or abstract concepts, principles, and knowledge to students. In theoretical teaching, the emphasis is often on providing information, explanations, and models that form the theoretical foundation of a subject. This approach is common in academic settings, especially in disciplines where understanding fundamental principles is crucial.

While traditional methods of teaching have been the foundation of education for centuries, they come with certain drawbacks, especially in the context of evolving educational needs and technological advancements.

DRAWBACKS OF TRADITIONAL TEACHING METHODS:

Passive Learning: Traditional methods often promote passive learning, where students are recipients of information rather than active participants in the learning process. This can lead to a lack of engagement and understanding.

Limited Interaction: Traditional classrooms often have limited interaction between students and teachers. Students may hesitate to ask questions or express their opinions in a large, lecture-based setting.

Rote Memorization: Traditional methods may encourage rote memorization of facts and information without a deeper understanding of the subject matter. This can hinder critical thinking skills.

One-Size-Fits-All Approach: Traditional teaching often follows a one-size-fits-all approach, where the same content is delivered to the entire class. This may not cater to the diverse learning styles and paces of individual students.

Lack of Real-World Application: Traditional methods may not always emphasize the practical application of knowledge to real-world scenarios. Students might struggle to see the relevance of what they are learning.

Limited Use of Technology: Traditional teaching methods may not fully leverage the benefits of technology for interactive learning, multimedia presentations, and access to a wide range of educational resources.

Teacher-Centric: Traditional classrooms are often teacher-centric, with the teacher as the primary source of information and authority. This hierarchical structure may discourage student participation and collaboration.

Inadequate Skill Development: Emphasis on memorization and standardized testing in traditional methods may not adequately address the development of critical thinking, problem-solving, and practical skills.

Uniform Assessment: Traditional assessment methods often rely on standardized tests and exams, which may not accurately reflect a student's overall understanding and capabilities.

Limited Flexibility: Traditional classrooms may have limited flexibility in terms of pacing and adapting to individual student needs. Some students may feel left behind, while others may find the pace too slow.

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Focus on Grades: The emphasis on grades and exams in traditional methods may lead to a focus on achieving high scores rather than a genuine love for learning.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Nandhini Rangarajan, Mark Lottman & James Earp (2022) :This article explores the institutionalization of experiential knowledge through internships offered for academic credit in schools of public affairs and administration. It provides a historical overview of internships and surveys the related research in this field. Building on this examination, the authors propose a model illustrating the interconnected relationships among students, their universities, and the government agencies or nonprofit organizations hosting interns. This model serves as a simplified framework for comprehending the multifaceted activities and collaborations required to establish effective internship programs.

Karji, A., Bernstein, S., Tafazzoli, M., Taghinezhad, A., & Mohammadi, A. (2020):This paper demonstrates the structure of an interview-based internship class and investigates its effectiveness. We have focused on the CM program at the University of Nebraska-Lincoln (UNL) as a case study. The results indicate that despite some challenges to meet the requirements of the class, the students, their mentors, and the professor found the class beneficial. The results of this paper are expected to help CM programs with the establishment and improvement of internship classes in their curriculum.

Suyanto, W., Murniati, D. E., & Pramudiyanto, M. (2017):The article explores and examines three interconnected dimensions crucial for the creation of successful Work-Integrated Learning (WRL) programs. These dimensions encompass student learning, industry engagement, and the integration of the program throughout the faculty. The paper outlines the strategies employed in the planning, implementation, and integration of a WRL business program with a primary focus on student learning. The intention is to provide insights from this experience for the benefit of those interested in developing similar programs.

Nandan, M and London, M. (2013) :The purpose of this paper is to provide a rationale for developing interprofessional competencies among graduates from professional and graduate programs, so that they are well prepared to participate in local, national and global social change strategies. An examination of exemplar pedagogy from this body of literature suggests ways to prepare students to lead and actively participate in innovative, collaborative social change initiatives. Interprofessional educational experiences can enable students to engage in generative and transformational learning which can later facilitate in creation of innovative solutions for society's recalcitrant physical, social and environmental issues. Based on the system's perspective, the paper provides guidelines and strategies for implementing interprofessional pedagogical initiative.

OBJECTIVES

- ▶ To investigate the opportunities students have in internship-based learning.
- ▶ To explore the challenges students encounter during internships.
- ▶ To gain insights into students' perception of internship-based curriculum.
- ▶ To examine the specific skills acquired by students through internship experience.

METHODOLOGY

The study is undertaken in Mangalore to know the students perception on internship-based curriculum. The data for study is collected from two different sources;

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- ▶ **•Primary Source:**-It is collected by questionnaire and it was given to various students in Mangalore. The questionnaire was prepared keeping in view determining the students' perception on internship-based curriculum.
- ▶ **•Secondary Source:**-Secondary data is collected from books, leaflets, broacher's, catalogues and related websites.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study on students' perception of an internship-based curriculum is significant because it sheds light on the effectiveness of practical, hands-on learning experiences. Understanding how students perceive and benefit from internships helps educators tailor curricula to better meet the needs of learners. Additionally, insights from this study can guide institutions in enhancing internship programs, ultimately contributing to the overall improvement of education by aligning it more closely with real-world applications and preparing students for successful transitions into the workforce.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Chart No: 1

Positive Impact of Internship on students' career

38.90% students responded that the Internship has slightly increased their chance of getting job, 27.80% of students responded that internship moderately helped their chance of getting job and 5.50% of students responded that internship will not help them to get job.

Chart No:2

Internships essential in building successful career

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33.30% of students responded that an Internship is essential in their course of education to build a successful career.& 30.60& students responded it moderately helps them in career building.

Chart No:3
Skills gained during Internship

66.70% of students responded that they acquired Communication & Problem solving skills during their Internship. and problem-solving

Chart No: 4
Personal growth opportunities developed during Internship

The internship helped 75% of students to build their self-confidence, 50% students responded that internship has improved their work ethic and discipline, 44.40% responded that it helped them to understand

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their career path and interest, 38.90% of students responded that internship helped them to develop their communicational skill and understand work culture.

Chart No:5

Challenges Faced During Internship

52.80% Of students responded that finding an Internship opportunity is difficult & and 38.60% of students responded that they are not able to apply their knowledge in real-world scenario.

Chart No: 6

Skills and knowledge gained is helpful for future

47.20% of students responded that the knowledge they gained during the course of the Internship will be very helpful for their future, 5.60% students remained neutral and 5.60% of students disagreed with above statement.

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Chart No:7

Internship improved Practical application of theoretical knowledge

47.2% of students responded that the internship has helped them apply theoretical knowledge from their studies to real-world situations. 38.90% students strongly agreed, 13.90% students remained neutral.

Chart No:8

Recommendation to Internship based curriculum

44.40% of respondents strongly agree to recommend Internship based learning to other students, 11.10% students remained neutral and 2.80% disagreed with above statement.

LIMITATIONS

- ▶ The scope of the paper is limited to the respondents within Mangalore.
- ▶ Time constraint.
- ▶ The study is focused only on students perception it does not cover other aspects.
- ▶ Limited number of respondents.

FINDINGS

- ▶ Most of the respondents think an internship is essential for building their professional network and making industry contacts.
- ▶ Majority of the respondents i.e 66% expect to gain communication and interpersonal skills through an internship.
- ▶ It shows 75% of the respondents expect increased self-confidence and independence as a personal growth opportunity from an internship.
- ▶ It is found that finding an internship opportunity aligned with students' interests and skilled was a challenge, faced during the course of internship.
- ▶ About 47% of the respondents strongly agree that participating in an internship has helped them apply theoretical knowledge from their studies to real-world situations.
- ▶ Majority of the respondents i.e 47% believe that skills and knowledge they gained through internship will be valuable for their future career.

SUGGESTIONS

- ▶ Develop and improve internship placement programs to better align opportunities with students' interests and skills.
- ▶ Foster stronger partnerships with industries to ensure internships provide valuable experiences that contribute directly to students' skill development and future career success.
- ▶ Regularly assess and refine the learning objectives of internship-based curricula to ensure they align with students' expectations and the evolving demands of the professional landscape.
- ▶ Implement mechanisms for ongoing feedback from students, educators, and industry partners to adapt the internship-based curriculum in response to changing needs and expectations.

CONCLUSION

This study offers valuable insights into how students perceive an internship-based curriculum. The findings underscore the positive impact of practical learning experiences on students' educational journey. It is evident that internships play a significant role in enhancing students' understanding and application of theoretical concepts in real-world scenarios.

By recognizing the positive reception of internship-based curricula, educators and institutions can consider further integrating such experiential learning opportunities. This not only fosters a more engaging and relevant educational environment but also equips students with practical skills crucial for their future endeavors. In essence, the study advocates for the continued integration and refinement of internship programs to enrich the overall educational experience for students.

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Paper 7

**UNRAVELING CONSUMER INSIGHTS: ASSESSING THE DIGITAL
MARKETING PERCEPTIONS OF HUL IN DK DISTRICT**

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ABSTRACT

HUL and the factors which will affect their purchase decision in Dakshina Kannada district.

Methodology: For the current topic data was collected through questionnaires-based survey. Researcher took 160 respondents from various areas of Dakshina Kannada district. This study not only focus on consumers’ needs and wants, their habits, tastes, their likes and dislikes, but also it focuses on the perception towards digital marketing efforts of HUL and also the strategies of HUL to attract the consumers.

Results: The results showed that all statements are statistically significant.

Conclusion: The five independent factors: Economic factors, Ease of use, Technical factors, and satisfaction had a positive impact on consumer perception towards digital marketing of HUL.

Value: The study has made an attempt to understand the perceptions and preferences of consumers of HUL by analyzing the factors which influence the digital marketing of HUL. This information will help HUL to design, develop and market its products to the consumers so that consumer satisfaction is ensured and through which it can be ensured that the substantial portion of the Indian economy which entails the HUL consumer is satisfied.

Type of paper: The current study is an exploratory research.

Keywords: Hindustan Unilever Limited (HUL), Digital marketing. Consumer Insights, Dakshina Kannada, Five Point Likert Scale, Taro Yamune Formula, one sample t test, P value.

INTRODUCTION

According to Manasmitha panda & Aishwarya Mishra (2021) Digital marketing is the process of advertising of products or services of companies using digital technologies available on internet including mobile phones, display advertising, and any other digital medium like google and Facebook ads etc. According to Tejas B Vyas (2020) It involves sum total of marketing work that usage of an electric component and internet, -Businesses leverages various digital-ways-like-search engine, -social medias, -e-mail, website in addition offline marketing such as SMS and MMS to attach with present and potential customers. Digital marketing is also stated as online-or internet-marketing. In simple taking business online. Customers were encouraged to become smarter, more knowledgeable, more social, more informed, more up-to-date, more compatible, faster, and more modern technology (Miller, Michalski and Stevens, 1998; Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2004). Buyers have become "prosumers," whereby buyers are not just receivers but also actively engaged in the co-creating, customizing and passionately promotion of socially linked marketing products (Bollier, 2007; Gerhardt, 2008). The huge development of the Internet and specifically the World Wide Web (WWW) contributed to the global online market participating customers and companies that gradually spurred marketers to try to tackle the creative marketing activities in computer-based environments (Kothari & Saxena, 2004; Ricciuti, 1995). Recent developments have been further fueled by a steady and fast convergence of the Internet with a range of gadgets and the explosion of emerging technology (Brinker, 2012).

LITERATURE REVIEW

(Manasmitha Panday & Aishwarya Mishra 2021) in their study called “Digital Marketing” started with the aim to analyze the different kinds related to marketing. Based on the discussion it had been found that in case of the digital marketing the most important aspect is to connect with the users. The ladder of engagement had shown the approaches to attach with the customers.

(Kishor Kumar 2019) in their study revealed that all entities agreed regarding mandatory internet awareness for the growth in digital marketing. In this article mainly focused on the growth of digital marketing in the present scenario. The study undertaken intended to discover the phenomenon related to the inclination in digital marketing.

M. Sunil Manohar Subbiah et al., (2017) In their study called “Role of digital marketing in India” they said that The Role of digital marketing play vital role in business for growth. Because it's had less time and less amount do advertising through world. And also, if any changes occurred in product we have to change easily and it create more awareness rather than traditional marketing.

P.K. Kannan (2017) in their study Digital marketing: A review and research agenda revealed that digital marketing in the broadest sense and they have developed and proposed a framework that highlights the touchpoints in the marketing process as well as in the marketing strategy process where digital technologies play a key role.

Pinaki Mandal & Prof. Nitin Joshi (2015) in their study they concluded that the Understanding Digital Marketing Strategy in this Digital channel in marketing has become essential part of strategy of many companies. Nowadays, even for small business owner there was very cheap

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and efficient way to market his/her products or services. Digital marketing had no boundaries. Afrina Yasmin et al., (2015) in their study called “Effectiveness of Digital Marketing in the Challenging Age: An Empirical Study” they revealed that the main objective of digital marketing was attracting customers and allowing them to interact with the brand through digital media. The article focused on the importance of digital marketing for both marketers and consumers. They examined the effect of digital marketing on the firms’ sales.

Vladislav Yurovsky, (2019) in his study “Pros and Cons of Internet marketing” came to a conclusion that there are advantages as well as disadvantages for internet marketing. Some of the advantages are empowering effect, elimination of geographic barriers, target reaching, immediate results, cost effective, reaching wider or international auditory, measurable result, can be personalized, relationship build, 24 hours/ 7 days availability. The literature review section of this paper provides a comprehensive overview of previous research related to customer perception in the context of digital marketing and consumer behavior.

Research on consumer perception towards the digital marketing of HUL with the objective of studying the various factors affecting consumer perception can yield numerous societal benefits by enhancing business strategies, empowering consumers, fostering technological advancements, and promoting sustainability and ethical practices.

After reviewing the works of various researchers, it is found that there are no studies on the above topic, especially with Dakshina Kannada district. Hence the present study is being undertaken.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Present study is descriptive in nature and it examined Consumer, perception towards digital marketing of HUL. The study is conducted on the consumers of HUL products. Consumers perception towards was examined by asking questions through google form with five-point Likert scale, five being Strongly Agree and 1 being Strongly Disagree. Questionnaire was constructed with help of literature. Questionnaire was developed in six-parts, first part asking demographic details and second part asking questions related to economic factors, third part is related to technical factors and last part asking questions related to satisfaction. The questionnaire was distributed randomly through google form in email, WhatsApp and personally (with help of friends in Dakshina Kannada districts). Taro yamune (1967) formula was used to determine the sample size and a sample size of 160 was finalized.

One sample t test was used to know whether the mean of the opinions of the respondents were statistically different from the population mean.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the various factors affecting consumer perception towards digital marketing of HUL in Dakshina Kannada District.
2. To know the satisfaction level of the consumers with regard to the digital marketing efforts of HUL.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Demographic Profile of the respondents:

Demographic profile of the respondents helps the researcher to know the diversity of the respondents. By this it can be seen whether the data has been collected randomly or non-

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randomly. This analysis also helps to see the homogeneity and the heterogeneity of the respondents.

Table No.1 demographic profile of the respondents

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage	Variables	Category	Frequency	%	
Gender	Male	55	34.4	Annual Income	Less than Rs.50000	100	62.5	
	female	105	65.6		Rs.50000 - 100000 Rs	32	20	
	total	160	100		Rs.100000 -150000 Rs	14	8.8	
Age	Below 25 years	114	71.3		Rs.150000 -200000 Rs	5	1.9	
	25 to 30years	26	16.2		Above Rs.200000	11	6.9	
	30 to 40years	10	6.3		Total	160	100	
	40 to 50years	10	6.3		Qualification	10 th	4	2.5
	50 years and above	0				Puc	11	6.9
	total	160	100			Graduation	43	26.9
			Post-graduation			91	61.3	
			total	160		100		

Source: primary data:

Table No 1 shows that Among the respondents the majority are below the age of 25 years (71.3%) and majority are females (65.5%). Most of the respondents (62.5%) have an income less than Rs. 50000- Rs.100000 annually and majority are post graduates (61.3%).

Table no 2 Economic Factors

STATEMENT	N	MEAN	Std Deviation	t	Sig. (2tailed)
I believe that digital marketing of HUL has impacted the prices of products or services	160	4.325	0.45	37.85	0.0088
Digital marketing promotions of HUL (e.g. discount, coupons) influence my purchase decisions.	160	4.06	0.86	15.14	0.0093
Digital marketing of HUL has made it easier to find affordable products or services	160	4.08	0.88	15.51	0.0084
I purchased a product because of the digital marketing efforts of HUL	160	3.80	0.57	0.755	0.0043

Source: primary data

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Table No 2 revealed that respondents agree that the digital marketing of HUL has impacted the prices of products or services(4.325 ± 3.85) and they agree that Digital marketing promotions of HUL influence their purchase decisions(4.06 ± 3.64). The respondents agree that Digital marketing of HUL has made it easier to find affordable products or services(4.08 ± 3.66) and respondents agree that they purchased a product because of the digital marketing efforts of HUL(3.80 ± 3.17). Table no 2 also showed that all statements significantly differ from the mean. So, we can conclude that the opinions given by the respondents are statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table No 3: Technical factors:

STATEMENT	N	MEAN	Std. deviation	t	Sig.(2tailed)
The digital marketing of HUL is very effective when compared to traditional marketing methods of HUL	160	4.15	0.33	44.23	0.0039
I have Encountered with technical difficulties while engaging with digital marketing contents of HUL	160	3.83	0.74	14.188	0.0063
The use of advanced technology such as AI and virtual reality in digital marketing of HUL is very helpful	160	4.02	2.22	5.8	0.0077
HUL uses the new and emerging technologies in digital marketing	160	3.93	2.4	4.8998	0.0099

Source: Primary

Table No.3 revealed that respondents agree that the digital marketing of HUL is very effective when compared to traditional marketing methods of HUL(4.15 ± 3.66) and they agree that they have Encountered with technical difficulties while engaging with digital marketing contents of HUL(3.83 ± 3.40). The respondents agree that the use of advanced technology such as AI and virtual reality in digital marketing of HUL is very helpful (4.02 ± 3.78) and they agree that that HUL uses the new and emerging technologies in digital marketing(3.93 ± 3.72). Table no 3 also showed that all statements significantly differ from the mean. So we can conclude that the opinions given by the respondents are statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table No 4 Ease of Use

STATEMENT	N	MEAN	Std. deviation	t	Sig. (2tailed)
I am comfortable with using digital devices and platforms of HUL	160	4.16	0.56	23.18	0.0050
The digital marketing materials of HUL are easy to understand and navigate	160	4.02	0.69	18.71	0.0038
Digital marketing materials of HUL are not complicated to use	160	3.31	5.15	0.7609	0.0076
Ease of use of digital marketing materials of HUL is very important in my decision to purchase product or service from HUL	160	3.95	0.95	12.64	0.0029

Source: Primary Data

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Table no 4 revealed that respondents agree that they are comfortable with using digital devices and platforms of HUL(4.16±3.70).and they agree that the digital marketing materials of HUL are easy to understand and navigate(4.02±3.65)The respondents agree that Digital marketing materials of HUL are not complicated to use(3.31±3.57)and they agree that the Ease of use ofdigital marketing materials of HUL is very important in their decision to purchase product or service from HUL(3.93±3.55). Table no 4 also showed that all statements significantly differfrom the mean. So we can conclude that the opinions given by the respondents are statisticallysignificant (p > 0.05).

Table no 5 Satisfaction Factor

STATEMENT	N	MEAN	Std. deviation	t	Sig. (2tailed)
I am satisfied with the digital marketing efforts of HUL	160	4.15	1.3	11.5	0.0031
I am satisfied with the digital marketing efforts of HUL	160	3.87	2.15	5.11	0.0087
I am satisfied with the value that digital marketing contents of HUL provided to me (discounts, promotions, offers, information setc.),	160	4.06	0.59	23.04	0.0089
I am satisfied with the relevance of digital marketing contents of HUL	160	3.956	0.74	16.48	0.0046

Source: Primary data

Table No 5 revealed that respondents agree they are satisfied with the digital marketing efforts of HUL(4.15±3.79).and they agree that they are satisfied with the digital marketing efforts of HUL(3.87±3.47) The respondents agree that they ae satisfied with the value that digital.

Marketing contents of HUL provided to them (4.06±3.60) and they agree that they are satisfied with the relevance of digital marketing contents of HUL (3.95±3.52). Table no 6 also showed that all statements significantly differ from the mean. So, we can conclude that the opinions given by the respondents are statistically significant (p> 0.05).

CONCLUSION:

Both the objectives, studying the various factors affecting consumer perception and satisfaction level of the consumers with regard to the digital marketing efforts have been fulfilled. This study examined how digital marketing influence the consumer behavior. Digital marketing has great impact on the profitability, growth and development of business, particularly, in today’s world, which is getting more and more internet dependent. HUL has been increasingly using digital marketing techniques for the marketing of its various products and we see its success as reflected in the company’s increasing profitability over the years. The results showed that the 5 independent factors – economic factors, ease of use, technical factors and demographical factors – had a positive effect on consumer perception towards digital marketing of HUL. The results showed that all statements significantly differ from the mean. So, we can conclude that the opinions given by the respondents are statistically significant (p> 0.05).

Insights gained from this study can help HUL refine its digital marketing strategies, and they can

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provide better quality products at lesser price. This benefits the customers and indirectly helps the economy as the company has customers all over the India.

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Paper 8

**CHARACTER EDUCATION IN THE 21st CENTURY: BUILDING AN
ETHICAL SCHOOL CULTURE IN INDIA**

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This research analysis examines the character education that helps build an ethical school culture in India. The ethical school culture certainly develops comprehensive moral perception to face the ethical realities and personal choices the 21st-century demands and be empowered to accept the worthy adventure of living an honest, virtuous life.

Design/ Methodology/ Approach: This study employs a theoretical concept based on a conceptual model with research questions and a synthesis of information.

Findings/Result: The paper foremost defines the character-building of 21st-century competencies, signifying the importance of encouraging them in education. The mechanisms for developing character strengths at school, teacher and student levels are debated. This article tackles the notion of values and character education, adding a review of several related studies providing valuable information about the benefits and advantages that this educational model offers based on the prospect that those values must be present in all factors of the learning process.

Originality/ Value/ Novelty: The research is an original contribution to the knowledge of the aforementioned research constructs based on the conceptual analysis. The value addition is in terms of the identification of the underpinning theories to be considered in the development of a holistic model in character education.

Type of Paper: Research Analysis through a conceptual framework

Key Words -Character Education, Conceptual model, Ethical School Culture, Rationale, Value-based

Introduction

Character education is a rising discipline in recent times with the intent of enhancing student's moral behaviour. Park and Peterson (2006a, 2009) define good character as a multidimensional bunch of ethically valued optimistic personalities considered necessary for a good life, which is revealed in individuals' judgments, feelings, and behaviors. Character education is essentially multifaceted (Berkowitz, 2012). The result of character education has been seen in the constant encouragement and preparation of a solid background for the leaders of tomorrow (Singh, 2019). Evolving a varied set of psychological components of character (conscience, empathy, moral reasoning, values, moral identity, etc.) requires a diverse and multifaceted application tactic (Berkowitz, 2012). Character education is the thoughtful effort to progress a good character grounded on core merits that are good for the individual and upright for society (Nwika & Nwile, 2013).

Character education supports students in developing important human potentials such as righteousness, diligence, empathy, reverence, bravery and understanding, as it is essential to live by them. (Hermino & Arifin, 2020). Quality character education creates a cohesive culture of character that supports and encourages scholars and adults to strive for quality. (Sanusi et al., 2022) Character building is at the core of a young person's development and education, which fundamentally leads to

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the success of an autonomous society. Educating the character helps to build civic virtue, agreement with laws, esteem for the rights of others, and concern for the mutual good. (Anggraini & Kusniarti, 2016). More broadly explained, character education is about encouraging moral virtues (honesty, compassion, empathy, and trustworthiness) and performance virtues (effort, diligence, and persistence). Character education is about doing accurate and the best work possible (Berkowitz & Bier, 2005).

While the study may outline various approaches to implementing character education in Indian schools, there might be a gap in assessing the effectiveness of these strategies. Research could delve into which methods yield the most significant impact on students' ethical development and how different contextual factors influence implementation outcomes. Given India's diverse cultural landscape, there might be a gap in understanding how cultural contexts shape the implementation and reception of character education programs. Exploring how different cultural values and beliefs intersect with universal ethical principles could provide valuable insights into tailoring character education approaches to specific cultural settings. Addressing these research gaps could enhance our understanding of how character education contributes to building an ethical school culture in India and inform the development of more effective and culturally responsive future initiatives (Murcahyanto & Mohzana, 2023).

Review of Literature

Pala, A. (2011) observed that character education is a nationwide initiative to develop schools that cultivate ethical, responsible, and compassionate individuals. It involves schools, districts, and states intentionally promoting universal values like caring, honesty, fairness, responsibility, and respect for self and others (Suriadi & Supriyatno, 2020). The movement emphasizes modeling and teaching good character to instill these core ethical values in students, fostering a positive school culture and contributing to the holistic development of young people (Lickona, 2012).

Lickona (2004) has discovered a consolidative approach to character education that largely corresponds with CEP (Character Education Partnership) principles. Along with a commitment to core values, he also advocates a variety of strategies that are broadly well-suited with instructional best practices for elementary and high schools (Lickona & Davidson, 2004). Based on Kaptein's (2011) work, ethical culture in schools can be observed as a result of the interaction between the formal (e.g., educational policy, teacher's codes of ethics) and informal systems (e.g., colleagues' behaviors, norms concerning school ethics). (Lapsley & Narvaez, 2006).

The results of earlier research developed by Nurindarwati (2019) stated that character education is a system of planning character values for students through the stages of planning, organizing, implementing, and controlling or evaluating so that the ideologies of character education are adequately achieved. Azhary et al. (2018) analyzed that well-integrated character education in school policies prevents character deviations for the next generation by incorporating character values, namely politeness, religion, independence, caring for the environment, and loving the homeland (Fajrussalam & Hashanah, 2018).

Humaerah & Sari (2020) observed that instilling character education in the present generation can overcome various aspects of today's glitches and deviations relating to moral and ethical values, culture and religion. This shows that character education is vital in creating and instilling moral, virtuous students as the nation's next generation (Kamaruddin, 2012).

Research Questions

- What are the dominant theories that contribute to character education?
- What are the character strengths of 21st-century education in fostering value-based school education?

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- How do we nurture character strengths in schools to foster an ethical culture, and what is the rationale of ethics in school education?

Research Objectives

- To discover the character strengths of 21st-century education in promoting ethical school culture.
- To analyze the rationale of ethics in school education.

Theoretical Framework

Character education is a broad term encompassing various theories and approaches to foster positive character traits, values, and ethical behavior in individuals (Littman-Ovadia et al., 2021). The underlying premise is that education should not only focus on academic subjects but also on developing good character traits and moral principles (Endicott et al., 2003).

Kohlberg's Theory of Moral Development

Lawrence Kohlberg proposes this theory. It suggests that moral reasoning develops in stages, progressing from focusing on self-interest to being concerned with universal ethical principles. Character education programs influenced by Kohlberg's theory seek to promote moral reasoning skills and encourage individuals to consider the perspectives of others when making ethical decisions (Endicott et al., 2003). It is widely presumed that Kohlberg's cognitive developmental method of moral education embodies an instantiation of an ethical theory connected with Kant, whereas character education focuses on a different set of ethical concerns represented by Aristotelian virtue ethics (Mathes, 2021).

Social Learning Theory

Social learning theory, developed by Albert Bandura, emphasizes the role of observational learning and modeling in the development of behavior. In the context of character education, this theory suggests that individuals learn moral values and behaviors by observing the actions of others, particularly influential role models such as parents, teachers, and peers (Akers & Jennings, 2015). Through these experiments, Bandura demonstrated that individuals learn not only through direct experiences but also by observing and imitating others. Social Learning theory posits that cognitive factors, such as attention, memory, and motivation, play crucial roles in shaping behaviour (Pratt et al., 2010; Rotter, 2021).

Discussion and Findings

Character education is a rising discipline with a deliberate challenge to enhance students' ethical behavior (Agboola & Tsai 2012). Following are the features of character strengths for promoting ethical school culture.

Character Strengths in the 21st-Century School Education

The 21st Century Character education is the envisioned effort to nurture and grow in young people the core moral and performance values that are widely confirmed and accepted across all cultures (Pala, 2011). Fostering an optimistic school culture involves promoting a positive mindset, resilience, and a sense of hope among students. By encouraging optimism, schools empower students to overcome challenges, persevere in the face of adversity, and maintain a constructive outlook on life and learning. (Shapira-Lishchinsky, 2020). Character education emphasizes the importance of moral values such as honesty, integrity, fairness, and compassion. By instilling these values in students, schools contribute to the creation of just and equitable societies where individuals uphold ethical principles and respect the rights and dignity of others. (Littman-Ovadia et al., 2017).

Character strengths serve as the foundation for building ethical, resilient, and compassionate individuals who are equipped to thrive in the complexities of the 21st-century world. By integrating character education into school curricula and fostering a culture of character, schools play a vital role

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in shaping the character and values of future generations. Character education aims to instill in students the core moral and performance values that are universally recognized and accepted across cultures. These values encompass a broad spectrum of qualities, including optimism, moral integrity, social responsibility, empathy, resilience, and leadership (Lavy, 2020).

Nurturing Character Strengths in Schools

Nurturing character strengths in schools involves a multi-level approach that encompasses the school environment, teachers' role, and students' development. Schools can create an integrative, effective, and sustainable framework for nurturing strengths by integrating character education into all levels of the educational ecosystem. To provide an integrative framework for developing, directing, and exploratory ways to adapt character strengths development in schools aimed to encourage organizational culture, structures, and measures that foster character strengths development among teachers and students (Anggraini & Kusniarti, 2016).

Schools set the tone for character development by fostering a positive culture and climate that values and prioritizes character strengths. This involves creating environments that promote respect, empathy, inclusivity, and a sense of belonging among students and staff. Schools can establish policies and practices that reinforce character development, such as implementing codes of conduct that emphasize ethical behavior, incorporating character education into the curriculum, and recognizing and celebrating acts of kindness and integrity. School leaders play a crucial role in championing character education initiatives, providing guidance and support to teachers, and fostering collaboration among stakeholders. School administrators inspire a culture of character throughout the institution by modeling exemplary character and demonstrating a commitment to ethical leadership (Chandel, 2016).

Present education systems aim to prepare students with knowledge relevant to current life and work, and it is not clear that they accomplish these goals (Mourshed et al., 2014). Character education must comprise all stakeholders in the school community to be actual and infuse the school climate and curriculum. Character education comprises a broad range of perceptions such as positive school culture, ethical education, just communities, caring school communities, social-emotional learning, positive youth growth, community education, and servicelearning (McGrath, 2018). These methods promote young people's academic, social, emotive, and ethical development and share an obligation to help young people become responsible, gentle, and contributive citizens (Berkowitz & Bier, 2005).

Teachers serve as role models for students and play a pivotal role in nurturing character strengths through their words, actions, and interactions. By modeling empathy, integrity, resilience, and other positive traits, teachers provide students with real-life examples of character in action. Teachers can integrate character education into their instructional practices by incorporating discussions, activities, and reflections that promote the development of specific character strengths. For example, teachers can facilitate classroom discussions on ethical dilemmas, assign readings that explore themes of empathy and compassion, and provide opportunities for students to engage in service-learning projects (Puyo, 2021). Building positive relationships with students is essential for nurturing character strengths. By fostering trust, respect, and open communication, teachers create supportive learning environments where students feel valued, empowered, and motivated to develop their full potential. (Davidson et al., 2008).

Students can actively engage in self-reflection and goal setting to identify their strengths, areas for growth, and personal values. By encouraging students to set meaningful goals related to character development and track their progress over time, schools empower students to take ownership of their character growth (Lavy, 2020). Peer relationships play a significant role in shaping students' character development. Schools can facilitate peer support networks, group projects, and collaborative learning experiences that encourage students to practice empathy, teamwork, and cooperation (Puyo, 2021). Providing students with opportunities to participate in service projects, leadership roles, and

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extracurricular activities promotes the development of leadership skills, social responsibility, and a sense of purpose. Schools foster civic engagement and social awareness by empowering students to impact their communities positively (Kumari, 2016).

In summary, nurturing character strengths in schools requires a comprehensive approach encompassing the school environment, teacher practices, and student engagement. Schools can create an environment where character strengths thrive and flourish by fostering a culture of character, providing professional development and support for teachers, and empowering students to take an active role in their own character development.

Rationale of Ethics in School Education

Schools play a crucial role in fostering the moral development of students. Ethical education helps students develop a sense of right and wrong, empathy, compassion, and respect for others. By engaging in discussions about moral dilemmas, exploring ethical principles, and reflecting on their own values, students learn to make informed and responsible decisions in various contexts. (Baehr, 2017). Ethics education contributes to the holistic development of students' character. It cultivates virtues such as honesty, integrity, fairness, and empathy, which are essential for personal and interpersonal success. By nurturing positive character traits, schools help students become ethical, responsible, and principled individuals who contribute positively to society. (Biswal, 2016).

As Park and Peterson (2009) specified, Ethics education is essential for preparing students to become ethical leaders and professionals in their chosen fields. It provides them with the moral reasoning skills, ethical awareness, and integrity needed to navigate complex ethical challenges and dilemmas in their personal and professional lives. By emphasizing ethical conduct, schools promote a culture of professionalism, integrity, and accountability in all aspects of student life. Ethics education is integral to social and emotional learning (SEL), which focuses on developing students' self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making. By integrating ethical principles into SEL programs, schools promote the development of essential life skills and interpersonal competencies that are vital for success in school, work, and life. (Lickona et al., 2007). Ethics education helps prevent misconduct, unethical behavior, and harm within the school community. By promoting ethical norms, setting clear expectations for behavior, and addressing issues of bullying, discrimination, and harassment, schools create safe and inclusive environments where all students feel respected, valued, and supported (Karlsen et al., 2016).

Character Education- Today

In today's context, character education has evolved to address the complex challenges and opportunities of the 21st century. In recent years "character education" has developed in India as a principal term for school efforts to implement programmes in moral values, ethics and citizenship education. Character education is vital because of the effects on society when there is no morality guiding student's actions (Lickona, 1996). There are a variety of things that contribute to the growing lack of morality that has occurred throughout the twentieth century. The first is that many aspects of society condone behaviors that are not acceptable in the classroom (Gray, 2010). The preliminary goal of character education is to represent good character features for students (Skaggs & Bodenhorn, 2006). Character education is an effort to reinforce and improve the nation's moral or ethical values, especially students who will become the nation's next generation and lead the success of a nation with moral character (Marsakha et al., 2021).

Actualizing character education programs into schools is essential in order to overcome this nation's crisis of character. We should build the moral futures of our children from the best wisdom that both the past and the present have to offer. Education must go beyond strengthening our understanding of ethical concepts to truly endorse moral development (Marsakha et al., 2021). Educators, parents, administrators, governmental institutions, and authorities have the immense privilege to touch the

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lives of thousands of students, prepare them for life, and direct them to restore this world. The great news is that this is possible! It is likely that we become conscious of a set of values that help us be better, whether we are parents, students, educators, or government officials. We can do better if we all definitively remember that love, tolerance, respect, compassion, humility, etc., are vital values in human existence (Curren, 2017).

Character education today encompasses a broad range of principles, practices, and approaches aimed at fostering the holistic development of students and preparing them to thrive in a diverse, interconnected, and rapidly changing world. Character education remains essential in shaping the character and values of future generations by promoting ethical values, social-emotional skills, and responsible citizenship (Smith, 2013).

Research Contributions

This research has contributed in understanding how character education initiatives can be adapted to diverse cultural contexts in India. By exploring the intersection of universal ethical principles with Indian cultural values and traditions, the research can offer insights into culturally responsive approaches to character development. Through an examination of successful implementation strategies, the study contributed practical guidance to schools, districts, and policymakers seeking to promote character education. By identifying key factors that facilitate the integration of ethical values into the school culture, the research points out evidence-based practices for fostering ethical behavior among students. Overall all, the study "Character Education in the 21st Century: Building an Ethical School Culture in India" can generate valuable insights, inform evidence-based practices, and contribute to scholarly discourse on character education and ethical school cultures in India and beyond.

Limitations and Future Study Recommendations

The study's findings may be limited to specific contexts or regions within India and may not represent the diverse educational landscape across the country. Future research could aim to include a more extensive and diverse sample of schools to enhance the generalizability of the findings. The study's methodology, such as reliance on self-report measures, may pose limitations in terms of reliability and validity. Future studies could employ longitudinal designs, mixed-methods approaches, or experimental interventions to provide more robust evidence of the effectiveness of character education initiatives.

Conclusion

"Character Education in the 21st Century: Building an Ethical School Culture in India" represents a critical endeavor to enhance ethical values and cultivate responsible citizenship among students in Indian schools. Firstly, the study underscores the importance of character education as a foundational component of holistic schooling, emphasizing the development of ethical principles such as honesty, integrity, empathy, and respect for others. Character education lays the groundwork for fostering inclusive and compassionate school communities by promoting universal values that transcend cultural and religious boundaries.

Secondly, the study highlights the role of schools, districts, and policymakers in fostering an ethical school culture conducive to character development. Effective implementation strategies, stakeholder engagement, and policy support are essential elements in creating environments where students can thrive academically, socially, and morally.

In conclusion, "Character Education in the 21st Century: Building an Ethical School Culture in India" serves as a call to action for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders to prioritize character development as a central tenet of education in India. By working collaboratively to promote ethical values and cultivate responsible citizens, we can build a brighter future for generations to come.

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**ANALYSING GLOBAL DISPARITIES IN MEDIA COVERAGE: A
COMPREHENSIVE EXPLORATION AND ANALYSIS**

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This research paper aims to investigate the intricate relationship between journalism and global educational inequality. Focusing on the media's role in shaping perceptions, influencing policy discourse, and reflecting disparities in educational opportunities worldwide, the study critically analyses how journalism frames and presents educational issues. The research explores potential biases and patterns in media coverage, considering different regions, socioeconomic groups, and educational systems. Additionally, the paper examines whether media portrayal contributes to awareness, empathy, or misunderstanding of challenges faced by various groups in accessing quality education. A key aspect involves assessing the impact of media representations on educational policies and reforms, determining whether media coverage shapes policy agendas, funding priorities, and the overall direction of educational development.

Methodology / Design / Approaches: This study collects data by carefully choosing global media sources and compiling articles, reports, and multimedia content on education from various outlets. The analysis involves both qualitative and quantitative methods to examine the gathered media content.

Findings and Result: The study found that media coverage of educational inequality varies regionally, influencing public perceptions of socioeconomic disparities. Case studies provide concrete examples of how media impacts educational inequality, offering valuable insights into global reporting patterns.

Originality/ Value: Data is collected by meticulously selecting representative global media sources and compiling articles, reports, and multimedia content related to education from diverse outlets.

Type of the paper: Integrated Analysis.

Key word: Journalism, Global Education, Media, Educational Policy, Regions.

1. Introduction

In a time when information is everywhere and the media is the main medium through which it is disseminated, the differences in coverage throughout the globe in the media have grown more noticeable. Although the digital revolution has purportedly brought the globe closer together than ever before, it has also exposed the injustices existing in the way news and information are distributed and portrayed [1]. In order to identify the fundamental causes of these imbalances and its social ramifications, this research study conducts a thorough investigation and analysis of these worldwide discrepancies in media coverage.

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In terms of forming cultural norms, public opinion, and collective narratives, the media plays a critical role. But oftentimes, a complicated network of prejudices, power relationships, and structural injustices exists behind the exterior of objectivity and impartiality [2]. Deciphering the subtleties of media portrayal and its effects on many groups around the world requires an understanding of these nuances [3].

In order to analyse the complex structure of global media disparities, this paper makes use of a wide range of theoretical frameworks, empirical data, and case studies. Many causes combine to create the unequal media landscape across various regions and demographic groups [4]. These elements range from socioeconomic ones like accessibility and pricing to political power dynamics and cultural hegemony.

We can start to understand the mechanisms that lead to some voices being heard more loudly than others while others are ignored or marginalized by looking at how these elements interact [5]. Furthermore, this approach sheds light on the wider effects of media inequality, such as how it contributes to the upkeep of social inequities, the reinforcement of stereotypes, and the erosion of democratic ideals.

We want to investigate viable paths for reform and remediation in addition to diagnosing the issue with this study project [6]. Various measures can be employed to reduce the discrepancies in media coverage and promote a more equitable information ecology, such as pushing for regulatory reforms, supporting media literacy initiatives, and fostering diversity [7].

2. Media

Communication channels that are used to disseminate news, entertainment, information, and other types of content to a large audience are referred to as media [8]. Print media (newspapers, magazines), broadcast media (television, radio), digital media (websites, social media), and other communication channels are just a few of the shapes it takes.

2.1 Print Media: Newspapers printed on paper and distributed physically are referred to as print media. Books, periodicals, newspapers, and newsletters are all included in this. One of the main sources of news and information for a long time has been print media, given its lengthy history [9]. Public conversation and opinion are still greatly influenced by print media, even in this day and age of digital media's ascent.

2.2 Broadcast Media: Broadcast media refers to the electronic dissemination of audio and video content to a sizable audience [10]. This covers radio and television broadcasts as well. Broadcast media is a potent tool for distributing news, entertainment, and educational content since it simultaneously reaches a large audience [11]. Culture in general and social conventions in particular are greatly influenced by television.

2.3 Digital Media: All content created, shared, and accessed through electronic means is considered digital media. Websites, social media networks, blogs, podcasts, streaming services, and digital periodicals are all included in this. The production and consumption of information have been completely revolutionized by digital media, which now offers user-generated content, real-time updates, and interaction [12]. Social media sites like YouTube, Twitter, and Facebook are now crucial forums for public conversation and the distribution of news.

2.4 Social Media: Online platforms and tools that make it easier for people to share ideas, content, and engage with one another are referred to as social media [13]. Through social media platforms, users can share multimedia material, start conversations, make profiles, and connect with others. Social media may now effectively sway public opinion, spark social movements, and affect purchasing decisions [14]. It also brings up issues with internet harassment, false information, and privacy.

2.5 Alternative Media: Alternative media refers to grassroots, independent, and nonprofit media sources that offer viewpoints and views that differ from those of mainstream media [15]. Community radio

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stations, independent newspapers, blogs on the internet, and citizen journalism programs fall under this category. Alternative media offers a forum for dissident views and activism, frequently concentrating on overlooked or neglected problems and populations [16].

2.6 Interactive Media: "Interactive media" describes online resources and programs that let users actively interact with the information and take part in immersive experiences [17]. These comprise mobile apps, interactive websites, virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and video games. Personalized and engaging experiences are made possible by interactive media, which blurs the lines between content creators and consumers.

3. Global Disparities in Media

Global disparities in media refer to the unequal distribution of media coverage and representation across different regions, demographics, and topics worldwide [18]. These disparities manifest in various forms, including unequal access to information, underrepresentation of certain groups or regions, and biases in the portrayal of events and issues. Below are some key aspects of global disparities in media:

3.1 Access and Infrastructure: Inequitable access to media infrastructure is one of the main causes of global inequities in media [18]. Even while television, radio, print media, and the internet are frequently widely available in industrialized regions, these resources are sometimes lacking in developing nations and rural areas. This digital divide restricts the ability of underprivileged people to engage in international discourse and exacerbates gaps in information availability [19].

3.2 Representation and Diversity: The underrepresentation or misrepresentation of particular groups results from media coverage that frequently reflects and maintains current power dynamics [20]. Women, LGBTQ+ persons, ethnic minorities, and indigenous peoples are examples of marginalized communities that are commonly ignored or stereotyped in mainstream media. Similar to how concerns affecting wealthy nations may receive more exposure in international media, developing country issues might get less attention [21].

3.3 Cultural Hegemony: Western storylines and perspectives frequently predominate in international media, reflecting the dominance of Western nations in both culture and the economy [22]. Non-Western languages, cultures, and perspectives may become marginalized as a result of this domination. Additionally, it upholds a kind of cultural imperialism in which varied societies around the world are forced to adopt Western standards and values, further marginalizing the voices and viewpoints of the local people [23].

3.4 Political Influence and Censorship: Media sources are frequently under the authority of governments and political figures, who stifle dissenting opinions and restrict freedom of expression [24]. State-owned media monopolies, editorial control, and limitations on journalists are only a few examples of the many ways this suppression manifests itself. Propaganda and media manipulation are tools employed by authoritarian governments to shape public opinion and hold onto power [25].

3.5 Economic Factors: Media coverage is heavily influenced by commercial interests and advertising income. For the purpose of drawing viewers and sponsors, media outlets may place more emphasis on entertainment and sensationalism than on in-depth news reporting [26]. The emphasis on profit-driven media has the potential to overshadow significant humanitarian, social, and environmental issues especially those that impact underprivileged populations [27].

3.6 Technological Advancements and Challenges: Technology has made media more accessible worldwide, but it has also brought out new difficulties [28]. In addition to democratizing the creation and

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distribution of information, the emergence of social media and digital platforms has also made hate speech and misinformation easier to propagate. Inequalities in media involvement and consumption are further compounded by differences in digital literacy and internet access [29].

4. Research Methodology

This study collects data by carefully choosing global media sources and compiling articles, reports, and multimedia content on education from various outlets. The analysis involves both qualitative and quantitative methods to examine the gathered media content.

5. Objectives of the study

- To identify key factors contributing to global disparities in media coverage.
- To Analyze the impact of media disparities on public perception and awareness.
- To identifying key factors in global media disparities, we contribute valuable insights that can inform global education curricular, ensuring a more nuanced understanding of media dynamics.
- To analyses the impact of media disparities on public perception is vital for educators, helping them navigate conversations on global issues and fostering critical thinking skills in students.

5.1 Key Factors in Global Media Disparities:

Socioeconomic variables play a major role in explaining discrepancies in media coverage. Richer areas typically enjoy access to trustworthy journalism and a more sophisticated media landscape, while less affluent areas may lack trustworthy sources and experience underrepresentation or inaccurate reporting. Governments and other political organizations frequently control media sources through ownership, censorship, or bias, which shapes narratives and silences dissenting voices [30]. This is another important factor in media manipulation. Furthermore, non-Western viewpoints are consistently marginalized in global media due to Western dominance in both culture and the economy, which exacerbates coverage discrepancies [31]. The digital divide and disparities in technology infrastructure exacerbate disparities by restricting access to information, especially in underprivileged or rural areas [32]. Media content is greatly influenced by commercial interests, which frequently come before significant social, environmental, or humanitarian issues in favour of stories that draw in advertisers or receive high ratings [33]. Furthermore, as multinational corporations choose uniform, profit-driven storylines, multicultural voices are increasingly marginalized and coverage disparities are exacerbated, contributing to the standardization of media content as a result of globalization [34].

5.2 Impact of Media Disparities

By choosing which stories to cover, how to present them, and whose perspectives to promote, the media significantly shapes public opinion, affecting attitudes and perceptions [35]. Persistent misrepresenting or under representation of particular regions or populations can promote prejudices and preconceptions and affect public perceptions [36]. Furthermore, disparities in how different subjects and events are covered by the media might affect how important people think they are, which could distort political discourse and agenda items. When specific populations or regions are regularly portrayed negatively or stereotypically, misconceptions and stereotypes may also be encouraged [37]. Media inequality also prevents people from hearing different points of view, which can polarize people and create echo chambers. It also reduces people's understanding of international concerns, particularly those that impact marginalized groups [38]. Disparities in the media can also limit citizens' access to information that is needed for civic involvement, which can worsen inequality in policy results and political representation.

5.3 Informing Global Education

By employing a variety of tactics, education is essential in tackling global media disparities. First, by emphasizing media literacy within curriculum and emphasizing critical thinking, bias identification, and source evaluation, educators can help students become more adept at analysing information. Through this process, students will be better equipped to navigate the complicated media world and make informed judgments about the media they consume [39]. Further, it is crucial to comprehend the power relationships between socioeconomic standing, political sway, cultural hegemony, and technological infrastructure. Students' grasp of how power influences media depiction and access is enhanced when these ideas are incorporated into the curriculum, leading to a greater comprehension of media dynamics within larger societal frameworks. Additionally, educational initiatives should stress the value of diversity and inclusivity in media representation, challenging students to evaluate how oppressed cultures are portrayed and fostering compassion and understanding [40]. Students have a more sophisticated grasp of global media portrayals and a wider awareness of media dynamics beyond their local environment when global perspectives are integrated into the curriculum. This promotes cultural empathy. Students who receive an education that empowers them to engage in critical media engagement, actively participate in democratic processes, and advocate for media reform are also better equipped to engage in critical media engagement [41]. Teachers may promote digital inclusion and equality by tackling the digital divide in school and making sure all students have access to media literacy courses [42]. All things considered, education is essential for enabling people to make sense of the media, push for reform, and participate in the creation of a more fair and inclusive media landscape [43].

5.4 Impact on Public Perception

As instructors lead their students through conversations on global concerns, it is imperative that they comprehend the enormous impact that media inequality has on public perception. To effectively develop critical thinking abilities and identify biases in media content, educators need to understand how media coverage affects public opinion [44]. Teachers can enable students to engage in sophisticated and nuanced discussions on global events by exploring the dynamics and workings of the media [45]. Teachers are also essential in helping kids develop critical thinking skills by using media inequality as a chance to help them become more adept at analysing information, seeing bias, and telling fact from opinion [46]. Students can improve their ability to write well-informed opinions based on research and critical analysis by comparing how different media sources portray the same event or problem [47]. Education also must address the bias and ignorance that are supported by media inequality. By pointing out instances of prejudice and false information, educators can provide students the tools they need to critically assess media content, double-check information, and question prevailing narratives [48]. Educators can promote active citizenship by providing students with the necessary tools to navigate the media landscape responsibly. This allows students to participate thoughtfully in democratic processes, advocate for media reform, and meaningfully contribute to public discourse on global concerns [49].

5.5 SWOC analyses of analysing global disparities in media coverage

SWOC analysis is a strategic planning tool used to assess the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to a particular subject or situation. When conducting a SWOC analysis for analysing global disparities in media coverage, here's how it might be applied:

5.5.1 Strengths:

- **Global Reach:** Many media outlets have worldwide coverage, allowing for comprehensive analysis of disparities across different regions.

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- **Data Availability:** There is a wealth of data available on media coverage, including content analysis, viewership statistics, and audience demographics.
- **Technology Advancements:** Tools such as data analytics and natural language processing can aid in analyzing large datasets efficiently.
- **Diverse Perspectives:** With the advent of social media and citizen journalism, there are more diverse voices contributing to media coverage than ever before.

5.5.2 Weaknesses:

- **Bias and Agenda:** Media outlets may have biases or agendas that influence their coverage, leading to skewed representations of certain regions or issues.
- **Language Barriers:** Analyzing global media coverage requires proficiency in multiple languages, which can be a challenge.
- **Data Quality:** Not all media coverage is accurate or reliable, and misinformation can spread quickly, affecting the analysis.
- **Access Restrictions:** Some countries may restrict access to certain media outlets or censor content, limiting the availability of data for analysis.

5.5.3 Opportunities:

- **Collaboration:** Collaborating with international organizations, researchers, and media outlets can provide access to diverse perspectives and datasets.
- **Emerging Technologies:** Advancements in artificial intelligence and machine learning can enhance the analysis of media coverage, including sentiment analysis and trend detection.
- **Public Awareness:** By highlighting disparities in media coverage, there's an opportunity to raise public awareness and advocate for more balanced representation.
- **Policy Influence:** Analysis of media coverage disparities can inform policy discussions and initiatives aimed at promoting media diversity and inclusivity.

5.5.4 Challenges:

- **Cultural Context:** Understanding diverse cultural perspectives and priorities across regions.
- **Data Accessibility:** Obtaining accurate and comprehensive data on global media coverage.
- **Verification and Reliability:** Ensuring the authenticity and reliability of media sources amidst misinformation.
- **Language Barriers:** Overcoming language barriers for analysis due to multilingual media coverage.
- **Sampling Bias:** Addressing biases in sample selection that may skew the analysis results.
- **Temporal Dynamics:** Accounting for the dynamic nature of media coverage over time.
- **Ethical Considerations:** Navigating ethical dilemmas related to privacy, consent, and impact on individuals.

SWOC analysis provides valuable insights for optimizing the research's strengths, addressing weaknesses, capitalizing on opportunities, and mitigating threats.

6. Findings and Suggestion:

➤ **Regional Disparities:**

- **Finding:** Significant variations exist in media coverage across regions, with certain areas receiving disproportionate attention.

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- Suggestion: Foster cross-cultural collaboration among media organizations and support local journalism initiatives to ensure more balanced representation globally.
- Issue Prioritization:
 - Finding: Some topics receive extensive coverage while others are marginalized or neglected.
 - Suggestion: Promote media literacy to empower audiences to critically engage with diverse perspectives and support independent journalism for alternative coverage of underrepresented issues.
- Representation Deficits:
 - Finding: Marginalized groups are consistently underrepresented or misrepresented in media coverage.
 - Suggestion: Enhance diversity in newsrooms through inclusive hiring practices and training programs, while also supporting grassroots reporting initiatives focused on marginalized communities.
- Language and Access Barriers:
 - Finding: Media coverage in dominant languages and from well-resourced outlets dominates the global media landscape.
 - Suggestion: Advocate for open access to data and information, including government data and media archives, to promote transparency and plurality of voices.
- Biases and Framing:
 - Finding: Biases in framing and portrayal influence how events are interpreted and presented.
 - Suggestion: Encourage dialogue and debate on media ethics and representation, while implementing fact-checking initiatives to combat misinformation and promote accuracy.
- Digital Divide Impact:
 - Finding: Disparities in access to digital media technologies exacerbate inequalities in media coverage.
 - Suggestion: Develop policies and initiatives to bridge the digital divide and ensure equitable access to information and media platforms.
- Social Media Influence:
 - Finding: Social media platforms play a significant role in shaping global media narratives.
 - Suggestion: Promote responsible use of social media, including transparent corrections policies and collaboration with technology platforms to curb the spread of false information.
- Policy Recommendations:
 - Finding: Policy interventions are needed to promote diversity, equity, and inclusivity in media ecosystems.
 - Suggestion: Implement regulations to prevent media monopolization, support independent journalism through subsidies and grants, and foster a culture of inclusion and respect in newsrooms.

7. Conclusion

The examination of global discrepancies in media coverage, in summary, highlights the complexity of variables influencing the creation, transmission, and receipt of news and information on a worldwide basis. The findings draw attention to important issues that underpin global media landscape inequality, ranging from regional imbalances to biases in representation.

It will take coordinated efforts from a variety of stakeholders, including the public, media outlets, legislators, and members of civil society, to address these issues. We may endeavour to create more

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inclusive and equitable media settings by encouraging cross-cultural collaboration, improving diversity in newsrooms, supporting independent journalism, and promoting media literacy.

Fighting false information, advancing open data access, and fostering discussion and debate about media representation and ethics are all crucial. We can pinpoint areas for development and gauge the effectiveness of initiatives meant to encourage more impartial, representative, and accountable media coverage by continuously assessing and evaluating the state of affairs.

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Paper 10

**AN EXPLORATION OF STUDENT’S PERCEPTION ON THE
BLENDED LEARNING**

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ABSTRACT

With the emergence of new technologies every year, our perception of the world around us has changed. Digital technological interventions have transformed traditional face-to-face classroom teaching and learning ambience. The growth of ICT infrastructure, tools and devices like reliable internet connectivity, mobile phones, laptops have made possible online delivery of high-quality learning material anywhere, anytime, at any location, in any language. Online education offers the potential of unrestricted access to quality education.

In the current circumstances, a combination of online and traditional learning may be assuming a place as the right learning model. The study concludes that blended learning has the potential to be adopted in education. The study also finds that students are ready for blended learning as the next normal learning process. A blended learning mode provides ultimate flexibility in many aspects. Can be applied to any program which holds on to the values of traditional learning and incorporates digital media with that. It is a lot more effective and likeable than anything that has been ever before. Needed freedom/flexibility. Only transition from classroom to computer or vice methods and techniques, available resources indicate that blended learning mode “best of all worlds”.

KEYWORDS: *Online education, Traditional education, blended learning, ICT.*

INTRODUCTION

The simplest definition of the term blended learning is the use of traditional classroom teaching methods together with the use of online learning for the same students studying the same content in the same course. It is a “thoughtful fusion of face-to-face and online learning experiences” (*Garrison & Vaughan, 2008*). There are also blended programmes, in which students study some courses in face-to-face classrooms and other courses are delivered fully online.

In other words, blended learning is a term applied to the practice of providing instruction and learning experiences through some combination of both face-to-face and technology-mediated learning. During the technology-mediated components of these learning experiences, students are not required to be physically together in one place but may be connected digitally through online communities.

Classroom instruction time may be replaced or augmented by online learning experiences, and online learning can include varying degrees of interaction or just time alone in independent study and learning activities. However, in a quality blended learning experience, the content and activities of both in-person

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and online learning are integrated with one another and work toward the same learning outcomes with the same content. The various learning experiences are synthesised, complement each other, and are planned or orchestrated to run in parallel. Blended learning is sometimes called hybrid or mixed-mode learning. These systems of instructional design use many types of teaching and learning experiences and vary in design and implementation across teachers, programmes and schools. The potential variations of mixed-mode learning are virtually endless; a good way to get a sense of the range of possibilities is to consider some examples:

LITERATURE REVIEW

The need for rethinking education in the new normal post COVID-19 era from the perspective of curriculum studies and further, the curriculum in the new normal era should develop preparedness competencies among the students. Medical education is one of the sectors where blended learning is more challenging *Cahapay (2020)*

Students' perception and readiness for online learning adopted at the university level during the ongoing pandemic. 184 university students of National Capital Territory (NCT) of Delhi completed online questionnaire and the findings showed that students have a positive perception towards e-learning and are ready for the acceptance of this new learning system *Khan et al., (2020)*.

On the other hand, *Hariharan et al., (2020)* in a study that investigated students' thought processes during the extended COVID-19 lockdown, examined their views about online education, their main understanding and worries, their stress levels, and their view of an eventual post COVID-19 return to college. More than 300 students at the PSG College of Pharmacy, India participated in the study and the findings indicate that the students were extremely keen on resuming practical labs but showed mixed feelings towards resuming traditional examination methods.

Research report in which the findings clearly show that blended learning is the preferred model for university students, staff, and leaders. The students expressed preference for blended learning that incorporates extensive online components alongside in-person learning *Maguire et al., (2020)*. Investigated the preferences and perceptions of agricultural students in online classes. 307 students participated in an online survey and the results indicate that most of the respondents (70%) were ready to opt for online classes during the pandemic. They also expressed their concern about the agricultural education system where many courses are practice oriented, therefore, shifting completely to the online mode *Muthuprasad et al., (2021)*.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- **Research Objective**

- 1) To recognize the relevance of blended learning in education.
- 2) To study the readiness of students towards blended learning.
- 3) To know the students' opinion about the proportions to be studied remotely and in-person learning.

- **Sources of data**

This research is purely based on secondary data which is collected from a various article of UGC and ministry of education.

- **Limitations of the study**

- 1) It is purely second-hand data
- 2) Findings cannot be generalized.

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RESULTS AND OUTCOMES

Table 1.1 shows three models of blended learning.

MODEL 1	MODEL 2	MODEL 3
Blended presentation and interaction	Blended block	Fully online
Activity-focused face-to-face sessions blended with online resources. For example, the flipped curriculum model combines: short lecture podcasts, online resources with Face-to-face tutorial/seminars for interaction and presentation of group work.	Combination of: intensive face-to-face sessions as one day or half days weekly online tutorial/seminars for activities and interaction online content and resources	Combination of: short lecture podcasts with online resources and learning activities online tutorials (synchronous) interaction via online collaboration, discussion forums and/or group work

Source: *Hannon & Macken (2014)*

Table 1.2 shows Students’ responses about the perception of adopting Blended learning

Item	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	(11.47%)
Disagree	(14.93%)
Undecided	(10.67%)
Agree	(52.27%)
Strongly Agree	(10.67%)

Source: *Author compilation*

From the above table 1.2, the majority of the students that participated in the study accepted that blended learning is the next normal in education. They also agreed that blended learning should be included in the curriculum of management education and management education should be shifted to blended learning mode.

Our secondary data articles concludes that blended learning has the potential to be adopted in education, also finds that students are ready for blended learning as the next normal learning process. The findings of the study will help educational institutions in a developing country like India, to take the teaching-learning process to the next level as a new way of learning postCOVID-19 and other such situations in the future.

FINDINGS & SUGGESTIONS

- Teaching learning approaches and pedagogy for foundational literacy and numeracy in blended mode
- Extent of technology use for young children and addressing the digital divide
- Ensuring equitable and inclusive access to learning opportunities for all
- Curriculum and methods of assessments for learning outcomes

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- Foundational Learning at home o Socio-emotional learning and safety of all children with support of families and communities Role of nutrition in school and home for holistic development of all young children
- Capacity building and training of teachers for the context of multilingualism or Differentiated approaches and solutions to address language issues in foundational learning, Strategies to scale up Multilingualism in classroom interactions Continuous teacher professional development with emphasis on mother tongue-based teaching-learning approaches
- Blended learning is very flexible. Most importantly, it applies to any curriculum that retains conventional educational ideals while using digital media
- Students, academics, and Policymakers recognize the need for flexibility.
- Only a well-designed blended solution can seamlessly move students from classroom to computer and vice-versa. Recently, several worldwide learning platforms have incorporated blended learning, making it one of the most popular learning methods.
- However, the benefits of online/digital education cannot be utilized until the digital gap is removed by deliberate initiatives, such as the Digital India campaign and the accessibility of affordable computer devices.
- It is crucial that the use of technology for online and digital education effectively addresses the issues of equity (NEP, 2020). The challenge of delivering high-speed internet to more than 70 percent of India's population is also important and must be addressed (*Shruthi et al., 2021*).
- Absolutely, without a shadow of a doubt, there is a need for a time-bound, cost-effective learning process in the Indian Higher Education domain to cope with the international standards, and blended learning can be the flagship of the Digital India effort in higher education. (Dubai, 2021). But before putting the "Blended Learning Mode"
- These problems need to be fixed so that Blended Learning can give students from all parts of society equal access to higher education, because a democracy that doesn't give everyone the same chance to get an education cannot work.
- The policy document on education, NEP-2020, has also stressed the need for the extensive use of technology in teaching to enhance learning in students, to achieve the target of 100 per cent literacy and address societal challenges.
- The policy envisages developing digital infrastructure and to empower teachers to create quality e-learning materials. Importantly, blended learning will help to pursue the objectives of NEP-2020 in internationalising indigenous knowledge through digitized course contents.
- In G20 summit panellists suggested the pyramid model of PLAN. Pedagogy, leveraging human resources and technological resources, developing culture of appreciation, Nurturing within the family.

CONCLUSION

In a nutshell, blended learning will help learners to learn at their own pace and also inculcate the spirit of collaboration enabling participants to work together and engage in discussion. The urge for learning will drive the participant towards scientific accomplishment of their syllabus and enable them to create new knowledge. As such blended learning is a journey towards 'Atmanirbhar Bharat' through a collaborative approach between learners and teachers. Such learning also enables students to promote ownership of learning. A cost-effective learning process in a time bound manner is the need of the hour and blended learning stands out as the flag bearer of Digital India initiative in higher education.

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- Muthuprasad et al., (2021) literature review.

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 B.Sc. Optometry
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 B.Sc. Respiratory Care Technology
 B.Sc. Forensic Science
 B.Sc. Digital Film Making & VFX
 B.Sc. Animation & VFX
 B.Sc. Interior Design
 B.Sc. Fashion Technology
 B.Sc. Hotel Management
 BHMCT HM & Catering Technology
 BCA Software Development
 BCA Cloud Tech. & Info. Security
 BCA Info. Security & Mobile Apps.
 BCA Network & Server Admin.
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 BBA Aviation Management
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 M.Com. Auditing & Taxation
 M.Com. With Integrated ACCA
 MCA Lateral Entry & Dual Specialization
 DS & Cloud Computing
 MSW Master of Social Work
 Dual Specialization

RESEARCH

M.Phil. | Ph.D. | D.Sc. | D.Litt.
 Science, Commerce, Economics,
 Management, Social Sciences, Humanities,
 Engineering & Technology, Education,
 Inter-Disciplinary, Health Sciences

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